

INSTRUCTIONAL CAPACITY AND EMOTIONAL QUOTIENT AS PREDICTORS OF TEACHING EFFICACY AMONG EDUCATORS IN REGION XI HEIs: A CONVERGENT DESIGN

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ABSTRACT

The study determined the influence of instructional capacity and emotional quotient on teaching efficacy, using convergent design. The data were gathered from higher education institutions educators in Region XI of the Philippines using sets of validated, modified survey tools with a five-point Likert scale and an interview guide. Mean, standard deviation and regression analysis were utilized to measure the quantitative data, while thematic analysis was used in qualitative results. The quantitative phase revealed that the level of instructional capacity was rated high, while the level of emotional quotient and teaching efficacy were rated very high. Further, instructional capacity and emotional quotient were found to have a significant influence on teaching efficacy. In terms of the lived experiences of the participants as regards teaching efficacy, six themes emerged such as embracing lifelong learning, showing empathy for learners, intensifying classroom management, alignment with organizational climate, curriculum-based learning, and maintaining emotional stability. The themes that surfaced on how their lived experiences shaped their beliefs included embracing of new perspective, creating new mindset, and awareness of school practices. Likewise, the themes emerged as regards the role of their lived experiences in shaping their attitude included advocating professional development, establishing proactive relationships towards colleagues and students, and becoming considerate of the needs of the diverse learners. Moreover, the themes emerged as regards the role of their lived experiences in shaping their commitment included intensification of code of ethics, demonstrating teaching effectiveness, and promoting life-long learning. Finally, the nature of data integration revealed merging – converging.

Keywords: *Education, leadership, instructional capacity, emotional quotient, teaching efficacy, educators, mixed methods, convergent design, Philippines*

INTRODUCTION

Teaching efficacy refers to the ability of teachers to successfully manage the responsibilities, demands, and challenges associated with their professional activity (Bugwak, 2022). Teachers play a vital role in ensuring high-quality education hence, teaching efficacy is the most critical factor in the promotion of teaching and learning excellence (Nyakundi, 2012). However, a meta-analysis study shows that many teachers are not committed to teaching due to poor sense of teaching efficacy (Rajkumar, 2020).

A study made by Pierce (2020) in England indicated that teaching efficacy of teachers has been disproportionately affected compared to other professions. A survey of educators from the Universities of Manchester and London found that 27.3 percent of teachers reported a low level of teaching efficacy which could have significant academic implications. In Asia, a survey conducted by the Center of Innovation and Collaboration (CIC) revealed that over 50 percent of institutions in Indonesia reported various obstacles to teaching efficacy, including issues with classroom management, lack of resources, high-stakes testing, and inadequate support systems (Dawadi et al., 2020).

Additionally, a systematic review published in the Asian Journal of Education highlighted the impact of teacher efficacy on their effectiveness and well-being such as external pressures, lack of support with 16-28 percent, lack of autonomy, and poor performance with eight percent, were identified as factors associated with poor teaching performance (Rajkumar, 2020). These findings collectively demonstrate the challenges faced by teachers in various regions, emphasizing the importance of addressing these issues to enhance teaching efficacy and overall educational outcomes.

Recognizing this, the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) in the Philippines has taken steps to promote quality education and inclusive social and economic development among teachers. Under CMO No. 52, series of 2016, the Philippine higher education institutions are required to serve as the appropriate platform for providing quality education. This initiative aligns with Republic Act No. 8293 Section 13.4, which mandates the Human Resource Development Service to design and implement plans and programs for personnel development, ensuring that the organization meets its manpower needs and maintains a positive work environment.

Furthermore, the Philippine Department of Education has acknowledged the significance of teaching efficacy of the teachers during challenging times. According to Briones (2020), the department considers addressing the poor teaching efficacy of teachers as a major challenge. This is crucial because low teaching efficacy can have a detrimental effect on teacher performance. Also, Montano and Acebes (2020) conducted a study involving 421 teachers from the Department of Education (DepEd) in the Philippines, revealing that 40.7 percent of the participants reported a moderate insufficient support system, while 60.3 percent experienced teacher burnout and perceived low self-efficacy in classroom management and teaching efficacy.

Numerous studies have highlighted the positive association between instructional capacity and teaching efficacy. For instance, Henson and Ellerbee (2019) found that

teachers who possessed a strong instructional capacity, including knowledge of content, pedagogical strategies, and classroom management skills, exhibited higher levels of teaching efficacy. Similarly, Darling-Hammond (2020) emphasized the importance of professional development programs that enhance instructional capacity, as they positively impact teachers' self-efficacy beliefs, ultimately leading to improved teaching effectiveness. Professional learning communities (PLCs) have been identified as a significant factor in enhancing both instructional capacity and teaching efficacy.

Adding on, Johnson and Donaldson (2021) suggested that PLCs provide opportunities for teachers to collaborate, reflect on their practice, and share instructional strategies. These collaborative environments foster a sense of collective efficacy, resulting in increased teaching efficacy among participating teachers. Effective teacher preparation programs play a vital role in equipping teachers with the necessary instructional capacity, consequently influencing teaching efficacy.

In the study of Wilson and Floden (2022), it was found that comprehensive teacher preparation programs that incorporate content knowledge, pedagogical skills, and classroom management strategies positively affect teaching efficacy. The authors highlighted the significance of rigorous and well-designed teacher education programs in building teachers' instructional capacity. The availability and utilization of appropriate classroom resources are crucial for enhancing instructional capacity and, subsequently, teaching efficacy. As mentioned in the study of Adams and Forsman (2018), teachers who have access to adequate instructional materials, technology, and learning resources report higher levels of teaching efficacy. The authors emphasized the need for schools and educational institutions to provide teachers with the necessary resources to support their instructional capacity and boost teaching efficacy.

The ability to regulate emotions plays a crucial role in teaching efficacy. A study by Sutton et al. (2019,) highlighted that teachers who are skilled at regulating their emotions in challenging situations reported higher levels of teaching efficacy. Effective emotion regulation helps teachers stay calm, make rational decisions, and maintain positive interactions with students, thus positively influencing their teaching efficacy. Emotional quotient also influences the quality of teacher-student relationships, which, in turn, impacts teaching efficacy. Added on, a study conducted by Roorda et al. (2017) indicated that teachers with higher emotional quotient tend to have more positive and supportive relationships with their students. These positive relationships create a conducive learning environment, leading to increased teaching efficacy. Training programs aimed at developing emotional quotient have been found to enhance teaching efficacy.

Likewise, in the study of Van Horn et al. (2018), revealed that teachers who participated in an emotional quotient training program reported increased teaching efficacy. The authors emphasized the importance of providing teachers opportunities to develop their emotional quotient through targeted training interventions.

Various studies have explored the factors that contribute to effective teaching, highlighting the importance of instructional capacity and its influence on teacher efficacy. Research conducted by Walsh et al. (2020) and Neugebauer et al. (2019) suggests that instructional capacity precedes teacher efficacy, indicating that a teacher's ability to deliver effective instruction impacts their confidence in their teaching abilities. Additionally, emotional quotient has been identified as a factor influencing teachers' self-efficacy. Also, Sangeetha and Natarajan (2019) found a correlation between teaching

efficacy and emotional intelligence, suggesting that instructors with higher emotional intelligence tend to exhibit more effective classroom management.

Further, Lakshmanan et al. (2011) conducted a study investigating the relationship between instructional capacity and teaching efficacy. Their findings indicated a significant relationship between instructional capacity and teaching efficacy, supporting the notion that teacher's instructional abilities impact their perception of their teaching effectiveness. Similarly, Uzunbacak (2018) discovered that instructional capacity positively influences teachers' perception of teaching efficacy.

From the literatures accessed by the researcher, it had been noted that some studies previously conducted dealt on variables like empathy, classroom environment, motivation, classroom management, gender, professional development, to name some, in relation to teaching efficacy (Noddings, 2012; Wang et al., 2015; Wu et al., 2019; Lee & Davis, 2022). These quantitative studies were bivariate in nature while the current study was multivariate utilizing mixed methods approach in determining the influence of instructional capacity and emotional quotient on teaching efficacy.

Consequently, the researcher had seen the urgency to undergo such endeavor and was interested in studying instructional capacity and emotional quotient as predictors of teaching efficacy among educators in Region XI. The findings of this study would contribute to the existing body of knowledge in the field of instructional capacity, emotional quotient, and teaching efficacy. Examining instructional capacity and emotional quotient as predictors of teaching efficacy is not only beneficial for educators but also for education leaders, particularly in light of the global health crisis that has significantly impacted the education sector. The shift towards technology-driven learning modalities necessitates education leaders to navigate through these changes effectively. Understanding the factors that influence teaching efficacy, such as instructional capacity and emotional quotient, can provide valuable insights and guidance to these leaders in managing and adapting to the evolving educational landscape.

Furthermore, the findings of this study may provide valuable feedback to educators regarding the importance of teaching efficacy and encourage them to further develop their teaching practices. Additionally, the results of this study could serve as a basis for drafting policies, recommendations and the development of appropriate, need-based, and research-based professional leadership programs. These programs can support teachers and school leaders in enhancing their instructional capacity and emotional quotient, ultimately improving teaching efficacy. This study contributes to the existing body of knowledge and lays a foundation for further research in the field.

Research Questions

The study determined the influence of instructional capacity and emotional quotient on teaching efficacy among educators in the higher education institutions in Region XI. Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What are the status of instructional capacity, emotional quotient, and teaching efficacy of educators?
2. Do instructional capacity and emotional quotient significantly influence teaching efficacy?
3. What are the lived experiences of the educators concerning their teaching?

- efficacy?
4. How do these experiences shape the beliefs, attitudes, and commitments of the participants?
 5. To what extent do the qualitative findings corroborate with the quantitative data?

METHODOLOGY

Locale

This study was conducted in Region XI or known as Davao Region. Region XI is an administrative region in the Philippines occupying the southeastern section of Mindanao. It covers 5 provinces namely, Davao Occidental, Davao del Sur, Davao del Norte, Davao de Oro and Davao Oriental. It has 105 CHED-recognized HEIs. Region XI is chosen as the locale of the study to help address one of the strategic objectives of CHED Region XI on human resource development was to enhance the teaching effectiveness of educators in the region. This study was carried out in Region XI, which was recognized for having educational institutions with many teachers and staff who could give reliable information about teaching effectiveness as predicted by instructional capacity and emotional quotient.

Sampling Method

In the quantitative strand, the respondents were the 296 educators teaching in higher education institutions in Region XI. Purposive sampling was employed in the selection of the participants. Purposive sampling is a technique that involves the selection of study participants based on the criteria set by the researcher, and this ensures the homogeneity of the sample population (Creswell, 2017). The criteria for selection of study respondents had include the following: must be a full-time faculty in their affiliated HEIs, must be at least three years in their employment, and must not hold any administrative position.

Moreover, the Raosoft sample size calculator was used to assist the researcher at all levels in determining the right sample size to be used in studying the above-mentioned population. The researcher chose a 5 percent margin of error since it was the common choice. Since the researcher did not know the population size, 20,000 with confidence level of 90 percent and 50 percent response distribution was used. The minimum recommended size of the study was 267.

In the qualitative phase, there were 17 teachers as participants in the study. Ten participants were invited to become part of the IDI, and seven participants for the FGD. As emphasized by Creswell (2017), a homogenous group may vary in size from three to four individuals to 10-15. These participants were chosen according to the inclusion and exclusion criteria stated in the quantitative strand but were separate from the 296 respondents in quantitative strand. The results of the IDI and FGD were utilized to explore the emerging themes based on their experiences.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher had undertaken certain procedures in conducting the study. An approval from the Dean of the Graduate School of the University of the Immaculate Conception (UIC) was sought to conduct the study through a letter request. Upon

approval, an Ethical Clearance was then secured from the UIC - Research Ethics Committee (UIC - REC) to ensure ethical soundness of the paper. After which, the endorsement letter from the Dean was formally forwarded to the presidents of the HEIs, who in turn forwarded it to the deans and program heads. After which, the researcher then coordinated with the deans and program heads for the schedule of the data gathering and interview.

In order to conduct the quantitative phase of the study, the researcher obtained consent from the respondents. The respondents were then informed about the entire study process, its goal, the various ethical considerations that have to be taken into account when gathering data, and that participation in the study was voluntary. The informed consent form (ICF), which was given to the respondents personally, was required of them before the survey questionnaire was administered. They were instructed to give the ICF back to the researcher as confirmation of their informed consent to participate in the study. The study's respondents only included individuals who signed the ICF. As soon as the respondents completed all of the questionnaire items, the aforementioned form was returned to the researcher.

The researcher gave the respondents the assurance that their comments were maintained in the strictest confidence and that their names were not revealed in any way during the course of the study. Additionally, the researcher made sure that the study was conducted without interfering with courses and that all ethical guidelines were completely followed. The responses were combined, totaled, and processed the quantitative data using the statistical tools.

In order to strengthen the study's qualitative component, the researcher conducted IDI and FGD. The qualitative strand's execution adhered exactly to the established protocols, just like the quantitative strand. The ICF, which indicated that participation in the study was voluntary, was given to the participants for signature. The participants were also aware of the entire study's procedure, goal, potential hazards, and discomforts. Additionally, they received guarantees that their answers were kept private and that they were permitted to protect their identities by using pseudonyms. Additionally, they were made aware of their rights to decline to answer the questions and to withdraw from the study.

Moreover, FGD was employed to gather together a small number of informants to discuss the topic of interest, in this case, matters of teaching efficacy. In the conduct of the focus group discussion, the researcher acted as a facilitator; stimulated the discussion or brainstorming through a carefully chosen topic guide which was prepared beforehand. This was to ensure that all the possible aspects of the study were explored. The discussion was audio-recorded, transcribed, and analyzed with the participants' approval, and unanimous permission for the recording was secured beforehand. The focus group discussion enabled the researcher to capture a richer and better picture of the given issue.

Instruments

In the quantitative phase, the researcher used an adapted survey questionnaire in gathering data from the participants. Also, the researcher recognized the original reliability coefficients of the questionnaire which was itemized in the later part of the methodology. This questionnaire contains the permission letter to the participants, part I which covers the personal information of the participants, and part II which contains three sections of adapted checklists.

In part II section A of the questionnaire, there is a checklist for instructional capacity. This was modified from Yalcin and Ereş (2018), which was used to evaluate the level of instructional capacity displayed by academic institution educators. It has 43 items with a Cronbach Alpha of 0.974. The instructional management practices, teacher quality, curriculum-material quality and quantity, instructional climate, students' learning readiness, and financial resources are the six criteria on this five-point Likert checklist. There are, accordingly, twelve, eight, five, six, six, and six indicators for each parameter. Additionally, the following scale was used to assess and quantify this checklist:

Mean Range	Description	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very High	Instructional capacity is always evident.
3.40 – 4.19	High	Instructional capacity is oftentimes evident.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderate	Instructional capacity is sometimes evident.
1.80 – 2.59	Low	Instructional capacity is seldom evident in school.
1.00 – 1.79	Very Low	Instructional capacity is never evident in school.

A checklist found in part II section B of the questionnaire was the tool used to gauge the emotional quotient of the educators. This is adapted from Tutorial point Emotional Quotient Questionnaire. This is a 50-item, 5-point Likert scale with the following parameters: self-awareness, handling emotion, self-motivation, using empathy, and practicing resilience. There were 10 indicators per parameter. It has 50 items with a Cronbach Alpha value of 0.975. Additionally, the following scale was used to assess and quantify this checklist:

Mean Range	Description	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very High	Emotional quotient is always manifested.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderate	Emotional quotient is sometimes manifested.
1.80 – 2.59	Low	Emotional quotient is seldom manifested.
1.00 – 1.79	Very Low	Emotional quotient is never manifested.

The questionnaire's part II section C contains the checklist that is used to evaluate the status of teaching efficacy. This survey is based on the work of Quang Duong et al. (2017), which has a reliability coefficient for Cronbach's Alpha of .920. The Likert checklist consists of six components: efficacy for instruction, efficacy for motivation and efficacy for classroom management. This checklist was scored and quantified using the scale below:

Mean Range	Description	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very High	Teaching efficacy of educators is always demonstrated.

3.40 – 4.19	High	Teaching efficacy of educators is oftentimes demonstrated.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderate	Teaching efficacy of educators is sometimes demonstrated.
1.80 – 2.59	Low	Teaching efficacy of educators is seldom demonstrated.
1.00 – 1.79	Very Low	Teaching efficacy of educators is never demonstrated.

In qualitative phase, the researcher used a self-made interview guide which was also validated by a panel of experts. This interview guide elicited the lived experiences as regards their teaching efficacy. It consisted of parts namely: letter of permission to the participants, part I or preliminaries, and part II or the interview proper.

The quantitative and qualitative questionnaires were subjected to content validation which was done by five experts. Also, the quantitative questionnaire was subjected to pilot testing. Likewise, revisions on both quantitative and qualitative questionnaires followed based on the consolidated suggestions of the expert validators.

Process of Analysis

The quantitative data were analyzed using mean, standard deviation, and regression analysis. The level of instructional capacity, emotional quotient, and teaching efficacy of educators were analyzed through weighted means. Standard Deviation was used to measure how much a set of values vary or were dispersed. A low standard deviation indicated that readings were likely to be very close to the selected mean. A high standard deviation, on one hand, showed that the values were dispersed over a greater range. To calculate the correlations between the dependent variable which was teaching efficacy and the independent variables which were instructional capacity and emotional quotient, multiple regression analysis was utilized to describe the relationships between the independent and dependent variables. Regression analysis produced an equation where the coefficients represented the relationship between each independent variable and the dependent variable.

For the qualitative phase, a step-by-step process utilizing Creswell (2023) was used to analyze the verbatim data gathered by the researcher through IDI and FGD. According to Creswell (2017) the researcher had to look at qualitative data analysis as a process that required sequential steps to be followed, from the specific to the general, and involving multiple levels of analysis. It started with an organized and prepared data for analysis. This involved transcribing interviews, optically scanning material, typing up field notes, cataloging all of the visual material, and sorting and arranging the data into different types depending on the sources of information. The researcher saw to it that all data provided a general sense of the information and an opportunity to reflect on its overall meaning. The researcher wrote notes in the margins of transcripts or observational field notes or started recording general thoughts about the data at this stage.

This was followed by coding of all of the data. It involved taking text data or pictures gathered during data collection, segmenting sentences into categories, and labeling these categories with terms, based on the actual language of the participant. Then the researcher used the coding process to generate a description of the setting or people as well as categories or themes for analysis. Themes and descriptions were then

represented in the qualitative narrative. Lastly, the researcher made an interpretation of the findings of the results.

Scope and Limitations

The use of the convergent design allowed the researcher to gain an in-depth understanding of the quantitative data using qualitative data. Further, the weaknesses of this research were offset by using both the quantitative and qualitative approaches. However, using such method entailed some methodological issues such as design, time, participants, technology, and resources.

Design. When using a convergent design, the researcher anticipated the issues during the collection, analysis, and interpretation of data. The procedure of converging or merging the quantitative and qualitative data had a tendency to reveal conflicting, contradicting, and varying findings. In relation to this, the researcher used strategies to address the above-mentioned issues. Some of these strategies included revisiting the alignment of research questions to the title of the study, scrutinizing the research instrument if all parameters, indicators, and statements were appropriate to answer the research questions, and also examining the questions used in the interview guide if all were parallel to the quantitative instrument.

Time. During the endeavor, the researcher allocated ample time to follow through the various procedures enclosed. The researcher allotted sufficient time in acquiring permission to conduct the study considering the varied protocols set by the respective target institution. Also, the collection and retrieval of quantitative data for a total of 292 sample sizes truly consumed more time in the process. In addition to this, the researcher exerted more time in setting and aligning the varied schedules of participants that were involved in IDI and FGD sessions. Moreover, the separate analysis and interpretation of both quantitative and qualitative data made the researcher endure for a longer period of time.

Participants Selection. During the conduct of the study, the researcher was able to experience sampling issues. In the quantitative phase, the panel suggested number of respondents was 250- 300. They must be full-time faculty in their affiliated HEIs, must be at least 3 years in their employment, and must not hold any administrative position during the data gathering period. In the actual conduct, the researcher resorted to changing the sampling technique to a total population sampling technique due to the following reasons: first, there were participants who qualified in the inclusion criteria but were not available because they were granted a full release study leave status in their schooling; and second, after reading the informed consent form, there were educators who opted not to get involved in the study as a participant.

Resources. Since it was a mixed methods approach and currently there is still a pandemic, the researcher utilized a private vehicle to carry out the survey questionnaire, IDI, and FGD. Moreover, since the researcher took considerable time from the participants to answer the survey and participate in the IDI and FGD, the researcher gave them tokens as a symbol of gratitude. This, in turn, entailed additional financial challenges for the researcher. However, the researcher allocated a budget for this purpose.

RESULTS

After the data collection and analysis, the study's results shed light on several key findings. The data are presented in tabular and descriptive manner.

Level of Instructional Capacity of Educators

Shown in Table 1 is the level of the instructional capacity of educators in private higher institutions in Region XI. It has an overall mean of 4.17 with a description of high. This shows that instructional capacity is oftentimes evident among educators. More so, the overall standard deviation is .55, which is less than 1, indicative of a minimal range of dispersion.

Instructional Management Practices. This indicator obtained a category mean of 4.18 with a description of high. It has a mean range of 4.06 to 4.32. The item, *sets instructional goals to increase student achievement*, has a mean rating of 4.32. The item, *provides feedback related to the lessons by meeting with the teachers*, obtains a mean rating of 4.06.

Teacher Quality. This indicator has garnered a mean rating of 4.40, described as very high. It has a mean range of 4.28 to 4.52. The item, *having up-to-date legislation regarding their duties has a mean of 4.28* while the item, *responsibilities about the subjects taught in the lessons*, has a mean of 4.52.

Curriculum-Material Quality and Quantity. This indicator has a mean score of 4.21, described as very high. It has a mean range of 4.05 to 4.32. Looking at the individual items, the item, *curriculum facilitates learning*, has garnered a mean rating of 4.32. While the item, *technological infrastructure provides opportunities for technological applications in education*, has a mean of 4.05.

Table 1
Level of Instructional Capacity of Educators

A. Instructional Management Practices The school management is...	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description
1. setting instructional goals with us to increase student achievement.	4.32	.76	Very High
2. conducting professional development studies of teachers according to the instructional needs of our school.	4.11	.87	High
3. obtaining information about teachers' knowledge, skills, and competence.	4.22	.79	Very High
4. monitoring teachers' instructional practices in the classroom	4.20	.85	Very High
5. implementing practices to raise the expectations of families about the academic achievement levels of students.	4.11	.84	High
6. creating high expectations for the success of students.	4.29	.74	Very High
7. bringing good examples of other schools related to academic studies to the school.	4.13	.84	High

8. ensuring that the education and instruction areas in the school are ready for use every day.	4.14	.82	High
9. preparing areas for the students to study.	4.14	.88	High
10. providing feedback related to the lessons by meeting with the teachers.	4.06	.86	High
11. monitoring the academic development of students.	4.27	.76	Very High
12. precautioning against situations (discipline problems, noise, etc.) that will disrupt the instruction time in the school.	4.13	.85	High

Category Mean	4.18	.68	High
B. Teacher Quality	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description
The teachers in our school are...			

13. responding to student questions about the subjects taught in the lessons.	4.52	.56	Very High
14. using instructional strategies that enable students to build their own knowledge.	4.49	.60	Very High
15. using strategies to cope with unwanted student behavior.	4.40	.68	Very High
16. getting in the class as being prepared for the lesson	4.44	.64	Very High
17. participating in studies aimed at ensuring their professional development (in-service training, graduate, etc.).	4.39	.68	Very High
18. running the instructional activities at the speed they are planning.	4.29	.68	Very High
19. constituting positive role models for their students.	4.41	.63	Very High
20. having up-to-date legislation regarding their duties and responsibilities.	4.28	.72	Very High
Category Mean	4.40	.53	Very High

C. Curriculum-Material Quality and Quantity	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description
Our school is...			

21. having materials for instructional activities that are to be carried out.	4.20	.72	Very High
22. providing curriculum which facilitates learning.	4.32	.67	Very High
23. furnishing materials in the classrooms are suitable for the age of students.	4.21	.76	Very High
24. having curriculum which is adapted to the student's level.	4.28	.70	Very High

25. providing opportunities for technological applications in education.	4.05	.84	High
Category Mean	4.21	.63	Very High

D. Instructional Climate The teachers in our school are...	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description
26. relating others based on mutual respect and trust.	4.26	.82	Very High
27. taking all staff in joint responsibility for student learning.	4.25	.77	Very High
28. having teachers eager to develop instruction together.	4.31	.70	Very High
29. having teachers who organize extracurricular activities for instructional purposes.	4.29	.74	Very High
30. sharing their teaching experiences with other teachers	4.30	.77	Very High
31. cooperating in carrying out effective teaching among teachers	4.30	.75	Very High
Category Mean	4.28	.64	Very High

E. Student's Learning Readiness In our school student are ...	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description
32. concerned with lessons.	4.05	.73	High
33. willing to take on their own learning responsibilities according to their age.	4.07	.75	High
34. eager to complete their previous learning deficiencies.	4.07	.75	High
35. doing extra study to keep their grades high.	3.95	.78	High
36. having the prerequisite knowledge and skills to perform learning.	4.03	.74	High
37. meeting their basic needs (health, nutrition, sleep, etc.) for learning.	4.07	.70	High
Category Mean	4.04	.62	High

F. Financial Resources Our school is...	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description
38. providing financial support to the teachers for the instructional activities they want to perform.	3.94	.90	High

39. having financial resources that can operate staff when needed.	3.95	.84	High
40. providing financial support for teachers to undertake professional development.	3.97	.91	High
41. having financial resources that can fulfill the desired instructional innovations of teachers.	3.92	.89	High
42. allowing teachers to access financial resources to enrich their instructional practices.	3.87	.94	High
43. having a parent-teacher association that provides financial support.	3.67	1.20	High
Category Mean	3.88	.81	High
OVERALL MEAN	4.17	.55	High

Instructional Climate. This category has a mean of 4.28 described as very high. The means for the items of this indicator range from 4.25 to 4.31. The item, *all staff take joint responsibility for student learning*, gets a mean rating of 4.25. The item, *teachers are eager to develop instruction together*, gets a mean rating of 4.31

Student's Learning Readiness. The mean score for this indicator is 4.04 with a description of high. It has a mean range of 3.95 to 4.07. The items, *students are willing to take on their own learning responsibilities according to their age; students are eager to complete their previous learning deficiencies; and students meet their basic needs* have a mean rating of 4.07. The item, *students do extra study to keep their grades high*, has a mean score of 3.95.

Financial Resources. This indicator has a mean score of 3.88 described as high level. Looking at the individual items, the mean ratings ranged from 3.67 to 3.97. The item, *the school has a parent-teacher association that financial support*, has a mean rating of 3.67. The item, *the school provides financial support for teachers to undertake professional development* has garnered a mean rating of 3.97.

Level of Emotional Quotient of Educators

Table 2 shows the level of emotional quotient of the educators in private higher education institutions in Region XI. This is measured in terms of self-awareness, handling emotions, self-motivation, using empathy, and practicing resilience. This variable has an overall mean of 4.20 with a description of very high. This shows that emotional quotient is always manifested by the educators in private higher education institutions in Region XI. Additionally, its standard deviation of .472 denotes that the responses of the respondents are closer to the mean.

Self-Awareness. The mean score for this indicator is 4.29 with a description of very high. Looking at the individual items, the mean rating ranges from 3.90 to 4.59. The item, *as a teacher, speaks out if someone has upset or annoyed me*, has garnered a mean rating of 3.90. The item, *as a teacher, know when I am in a good mood*, get a mean rating of 4.59.

Handling Emotions. Computations yield a mean score of 4.16, described as high for this indicator. The means for the items of this category range from 3.85 to 4.40, and the item,

as a teacher, I realize when I am feeling stressed has garnered a mean rating of 4.40. The item, as a teacher, I rarely worry about life or work and others often realize how I am feeling, has a mean of 3.85.

Table 2
Level of Emotional Quotient of Educators

A. Self-Awareness As a teacher I am...	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description
1. knowing immediately when I become angry.	4.49	.60	Very High
2. knowing when I am in a good mood.	4.59	.57	Very High
3. liking to know new people and making new friends	4.32	.77	Very High
4. meeting with different types of people.	4.20	.79	Very High
5. liking to interact with people and talking to them.	4.16	.80	High
6. realizing when I am being difficult.	4.27	.68	Very High
7. liking to be aware of my emotions.	4.38	.70	Very High
8. speaking out if someone has upset or annoyed me.	3.90	.92	High
9. controlling and manage my anger quickly.	4.21	.70	Very High
10. describing things that make me happy.	4.42	.64	Very High
Category Mean	4.29	.51	Very High
B. Handling Emotions As a teacher I am...			
11. handling bad situations fast.	4.09	.72	High
12. controlling over my emotions.	4.23	.67	Very High
13. realizing when I am feeling stressed.	4.40	.63	Very High
14. recognizing my emotions.	4.34	.70	Very High
15. knowing when and why I am anxious.	4.32	.62	Very High
16. changing my mood when I want to.	4.15	.75	High
17. avoiding stressful situations affect me or my work	4.27	.77	Very High
18. worrying about life or work rarely.	3.85	.88	High
19. suppressing my emotions as per my will.	4.06	.77	High
20. realizing how others feel about me.	3.85	.88	High
Category Mean	4.16	.53	High
C. Self-Motivation As a teacher I am...			
21. self-motivating.	4.41	.68	Very High
22. prioritizing between a set of important tasks.	4.40	.66	Very High
23. letting others find it easy to know my mood.	4.01	.86	High

24. losing my temper when dealing with difficult people rarely	3.85	.92	High
25. not getting annoyed with difficult people.	3.74	.95	High
26. doing the most difficult work first.	3.98	.90	High
27. liking bigger rewards later compared to small, instant ones.	3.93	.93	High
28. believing in the instant action.	4.03	.88	High
29. motivating myself to do better things while struggling	4.25	.73	Very High
30. getting motivated has made me successful.	4.41	.66	Very High
Category Mean	4.10	.57	High

**D. Using Empathy
As a teacher am...**

31. seeing the problem someone faces from his point of view.	4.19	.71	High
32. empathizing with others when I listen to their issues.	4.28	.67	Very High
33. meeting deadlines.	4.09	.78	High
34. utilizing time.	4.22	.72	Very High
35. avoid giving ambiguous messages or signals.	4.13	.74	High
36. realizing that people will have different working styles.	4.46	.65	Very High
37. realizing immediately if I am being unreasonable	4.18	.73	High
38. realizing the reasons behind my action hurting people.	4.22	.73	Very High
39. understanding things people are trying to tell me.	4.23	.72	Very High
40. knowing the reason that started the disagreement.	4.14	.75	High
Category Mean	4.21	.54	Very High

**E. Practicing Resilience
As a teacher I am...**

41. having good listening skills	4.33	.64	Very High
42. letting others complete their sentences before I speak.	4.26	.67	Very High
43. knowing when someone is unhappy with me.	4.26	.73	Very High
44. telling when people are not getting along well.	4.26	.69	Very High
45. realizing when people start being unreasonable with me.	4.25	.73	Very High
46. needing interesting colleagues to make my job interesting.	4.11	.90	High
47. asking questions to people to understand them.	4.22	.74	Very High

48. looking at working with difficult people as a challenge.	4.12	.84	High
49. ending differences with others.	4.07	.72	High
50. building strong relationships with those I work with.	4.32	.65	Very High
Category Mean	4.22	.52	Very High
OVERALL MEAN	4.20	.47	Very High

Self-Motivation. This indicator has a mean of 4.10 with a high descriptive equivalent. Looking at the individual items, the mean ratings range from 3.74 to 4.41. The item, *as a teacher, I don't get annoyed with difficult people*, has garnered a mean of 3.74. The item, *as a teacher, I am self-motivating and getting motivated has made me successful*, has a mean of 4.41.

Using Empathy. Computations yield a mean score of 4.21 with a description of very high. The means for the items of this category range from 4.09 to 4.46. The item, *as a teacher, I am good at meeting deadlines*, has garnered a mean rating of 4.09, while the item, *as a teacher, I realize that people will have different working styles*, gets a mean score of 4.46.

Practicing Resilience. The mean rating for this indicator is 4.22, described as a very high level. Looking at the individual items, the item, *as a teacher, I have good listening skills*, has a mean of 4.33, while the item, *as a teacher, I am good at ending differences with others*, has garnered a mean rating of 4.07.

Level of Teaching Efficacy of Educators

Table 3 shows the level of teaching efficacy of educators in private higher education institutions in Region XI. It appears that the overall mean for teaching efficacy is 4.44 whose descriptive equivalent is very high, which means that teaching efficacy is always demonstrated by the educators. Additionally, the standard deviation of .472 denotes that the responses of the respondents are closer to the mean, with less variation or spread between the individual data points.

Efficacy for Instruction. Computations yield a mean score of 4.47 or very high for this indicator. It has a mean range from 4.44 to 4.53, and the item *as a teacher, I can implement alternative strategies in my classroom*, has a mean score of 4.44. The item, *as a teacher, I can provide an alternative explanation for example when students are confused*, gets a mean rating of 4.53.

Efficacy for Motivation. It has a category mean of 4.44 with a description of very high. The mean ranges from 4.33 to 4.55. The item, *as a teacher, I can help my student's value learning*, garners a mean rating of 4.55. The item, *as a teacher, I can provide an alternative explanation for example when students are confused*, has a mean rating of 4.33.

Table 3
Level of Teaching Efficacy of Educators

A. Efficacy for Instruction As a teacher, I am...	Mean	Std. Deviation	Description
1. responding to difficult questions from my students.	4.45	.56	Very High
2. providing appropriate challenges for very capable students.	4.45	.58	Very High
3. implementing alternative strategies in my classroom.	4.44	.60	Very High
4. providing an alternative explanation for example when students are confused.	4.53	.56	Very High
Category Mean	4.47	.50	Very High
<hr/>			
B. Efficacy for Motivation As a teacher, I am...	Mean	Std. Deviation	Description
5. helping my student's value learning.	4.55	.54	Very High
6. providing appropriate challenges for very capable students.	4.48	.59	Very High
7. implementing alternative strategies in my classroom.	4.41	.63	Very High
8. providing an alternative explanation for example when students are confused.	4.33	.64	Very High
Category Mean	4.44	.51	Very High
<hr/>			
C. Efficacy for Classroom Management As a teacher, I am...	Mean	Std. Deviation	Description
9. making my expectations clear about student behavior.	4.41	.59	Very High
10. getting students to follow classroom rules.	4.46	.61	Very High
11. controlling disruptive behavior in the classroom.	4.42	.63	Very High
12. keeping a few problems students from ruining an entire lesson.	4.40	.61	Very High
Category Mean	4.42	.53	Very High
<hr/>			
OVERALL MEAN	4.44	.47	Very High

Efficacy for Classroom Management. This indicator has garnered a mean of 4.42 with a description of very high. It has a mean range from 4.40 to 4.46. The item, *as a teacher, I can keep a few problems students from ruining an entire lesson*, has a mean rating of 4.40, while the item *as a teacher, I can you get students to follow classroom rules*, got a mean rating of 4.46.

Significance of the Influence of Instructional Capacity and Emotional Quotient on Teaching Efficacy

Table 4 presents the results of the regression analysis regarding the influence of instructional Capacity and emotional quotient on teaching efficacy. It appears that the standardized coefficient beta for instructional capacity is 0.196 with $p < 0.001$ or significant,

while the emotional quotient has a standardized coefficient of 0.611 with $p < 0.001$ or significant. This denotes that for every unit increase in an instructional capacity, there is a corresponding increase in teaching efficacy by 0.196 standard deviations. Further, for every unit increase in the emotional quotient, there is a corresponding increase in teaching efficacy by 0.611 standard deviations.

Meanwhile, the R-value for the combined instructional capacity and emotional quotient is 0.749 with an R-square of 0.562, an F-ratio of 187.782, and a p-value of less than 0.001 or significant. This indicates that both instructional capacity and emotional

Table 4
Significance of the Influence of Instructional Capacity and Emotional Quotient on Teaching Efficacy

Predictors	Standardized Coefficients Beta	t	p-value	Interpretation
Instructional Capacity	.196	3.954	.000	Significant
Emotional Quotient	.611	12.298	.000	Significant

R = .749
R Square = .562
F = 187.782
p value = .000

quotient have a 56.2 percent influence on teaching efficacy. Thus, 43.8 percent of the variation can be attributed to other factors aside from the two independent variables.

Profile of the Participants

In the qualitative phase of the study, 17 HEIs educators from Region XI were purposively chosen as participants. There were 10 chosen for the IDI and seven for the FGD. The researcher assigned pseudonyms to each participant and divulged some data like sex, study group, and address only, in order to safeguard the identities of the participants and the confidentiality of the schools involved in this study. Table 5.1 provides a list of them.

As seen in Table 5.1, 17 educators from HEIs in Region XI voluntarily engaged in the qualitative component of the study. All participants met the requirements for being included as study informants. Eight of the participants were men, while the remaining nine were women, as shown in the table. Both the IDI and FGD were conducted online and in person, respectively. The participants were also invited to share their own experiences with regard to their teaching efficacy. The information or data elicited from the participants were transcribed, coded, grouped, and organized into themes.

**Table 5.1
Profile of the Participants**

Participant No.	Pseudonyms of the Participants	Sex	Data Source Group	Division
01	Mely	F	IDI	Davao City
02	Alex	M	IDI	Davao del Norte
03	Beboy	M	IDI	Davao de Oro
04	Angel	F	IDI	Davao City
05	Joel	M	IDI	Davao del Norte
06	Mary	F	IDI	Davao Oriental
07	Queen	F	IDI	Davao del Sur
08	Harry	M	IDI	Davao del Sur
09	Ken	M	IDI	Davao City
10	Precious	F	IDI	Davao Oriental
01	Myr	F	FGD	Davao City
02	Ron	M	FGD	Davao del Norte
03	Det	M	FGD	Davao City
04	Dan	M	FGD	Davao City
05	Jen	F	FGD	Davao de Oro
06	Che	F	FGD	Davao City
07	Myk	F	FGD	Davao Oriental

Lived Experiences of Educators Concerning Their Teaching Efficacy

Shown in Table 5.2 the data as regards the lived experiences of educators concerning their teaching efficacy. Six themes emerged from the responses of the participants concerning their teaching efficacy. These are as follows: embracing lifelong learning, showing empathy for learners intensifying classroom management; alignment

**Table 5.2
Lived Experiences of Educators Concerning
their Teaching Efficacy**

Themes	Core Ideas
Embracing life-long learning	believing that teaching is a continuous learning process being certain that there is still room for improvement being convinced that there are more things to explore to achieve effective learning practicing mentorship which helps a lot in teaching efficacy pursuing professional development by enlisting in graduate school programs and attending training and seminars
Showing empathy for learners	being happy to hear challenging questions from students being responsive to students' questions honestly and briefly by sharing what is known and doing research to answer challenging questions practicing unlocking difficulties by translating English to Tagalog or even

	<p>in Bisaya being considerate of the students' sensitivity paying attention to the student's needs. using differentiated instruction to cater to the multiple intelligences of the students</p>
Intensifying classroom management	<p>strengthening collaborative activities utilizing the leadership skills of the students practicing the beg, borrow and steal ideas from colleagues' classroom management observing open communications experiencing constant classroom monitoring</p>
Alignment with organizational climate	<p>experiencing relationships based on respect and trust in the institution willing to serve beyond the call of duty feeling under pressure when around other instructors having a cordon-free atmosphere observing student-friendly environment</p>
Curriculum-based learning	<p>following strictly the requirements of the Commission of Higher Education Memorandum Orders constantly improving the instructional materials used aligning the curriculum with the visions and missions carrying out activities that are aligned to the vision, mission, and goals of the school using instructional materials and teaching strategies that are appropriate to the students having a flexible curriculum maximizing the use of technology</p>
Maintaining emotional stability	<p>being confident that the school will back them up enjoying fringe benefits showing readiness in engaging the students to different activities being cooperative and happy experiencing healthy competition being motivated to teach</p>

with organizational climate; curriculum-based learning; and maintaining emotional stability.

Embracing Lifelong Learning. Participants in the IDI and FGD showed a strong belief in the teaching profession's ongoing learning process, a recognition of the need for improvement, and an openness to trying new approaches to achieve effective learning. Further, they stress the value of mentoring, continuous learning process, and the pursuit of professional development through graduate studies, participation in workshops, and attending seminars. These are clear from the participants' responses, which are as follows:

It is a continuous learning process for me to inculcate my students with new techniques and new lessons.

- Alex

We are aware that teaching is a lifetime learning endeavor... I still have a lot to learn. - Ron

As we all know, that learning is a lifetime process, and learning will not stop, but it will continue. - Jen

It's more of the things that I need to explore. Like, what's new in teaching and learning and what strategies needed to learn out from it. - Queen

Aside from the mentoring that she's giving me after class observations...lets me join seminars and training to enhance my knowledge and skills. – Det

The participants expressed a strong belief that they can enhance their teaching efficacy further. They acknowledged that no matter how experienced they are, there are always areas where they can improve and refine their teaching strategies. Further, they uttered a conviction that effective learning requires continuous exploration. Moreover, they highlighted the importance of mentorship in improving teaching efficacy. They shared a firm belief that learning is a lifelong endeavor that does not cease with the completion of formal education. In addition, the significance of professional development opportunities was also highlighted.

Showing Empathy for Learners. The participants expressed empathy for their learners as evidenced in their actual responses.

That is why when they ask a certain question that I did not know, I answer them honestly. - Ken

I-answer nako sya right away. Pero if ... unsure ko sa akong answer, maghonest pud ko sa mga bata nga I need to search about it ... - Precious

I answer right away. But If ... unsure of my answer, I will be honest to the students that I need to research about it.

real life scenario...na marelata doon sa topic para mawala yung ...confusion...gina-translate sa tagalog, sa bisaya,..para maunawaan. - Beboy

real-life situations ... that will relate to the topic to avoid confusion. I translate it into Tagalog or Bisaya...in order for them to understand.

...ask them questions in such a way that they could relate ...since our students now are very sensitive. They are Gen Z ...students. - Mary

As teachers, sometimes we have to utilize a lot of strategies to cater to the multiple intelligences of the students in the classroom. - Myr

Based on the results, the participants valued and appreciated challenging questions from students, recognizing the importance of fostering a culture of curiosity and critical thinking in the classroom. They emphasized the importance of being responsive and honest when addressing students' questions, sharing their existing knowledge, and conducting further research when necessary. Further, some participants mentioned the practice of unlocking difficulties by translating concepts from English to Tagalog or even Bisaya, which indicates their efforts to facilitate understanding for students who may have language barriers. Furthermore, consideration for students' sensitivity and individual needs were highlighted as the participants pay attention to their students' emotional well-being. Moreover, the use of differentiated instruction was mentioned by the participant as a strategy to accommodate the various learning styles and multiple intelligences of the students.

Intensifying classroom management. The said participants, when asked on the topic concerning their teaching efficacy, they provided specific statements.

I keep on telling them that no one should be left behind. I use collaborative activities...everyone will do his or her part as a team. - Dan

Mas madaling maintindihan ng mga students kung mismo sila-sila lang din yung mag-discuss. That is why I use peer teaching. - Jen

Easier to understand if they discuss it among themselves. That is why I use peer teaching also.

Peer teaching...group together with those who are on the lower level... help in facilitating the learning of their classmates. - Myr

I have to instill in them that no one should be left behind. That is why we are more on collaboration and cooperation. - Che

We have constant classroom monitoring that is why we need to have a good classroom management. - Harry

These narratives indicate that the participants' statements highlighted several important strategies for enhancing teaching efficacy which is focused on intensifying classroom management. As stated, strengthening collaborative activities within the classroom fosters active learning and engagement, while recognizing and utilizing students' leadership skills empowers them and encourages responsibility. The experience of constant classroom monitoring showcases a commitment to ongoing assessment and adaptation. By implementing these strategies, teachers can create dynamic and student-centered learning environments that promote collaboration, leadership, learning from peers, open communication, and continuous monitoring, implying that educators intensify classroom management to address the educational needs of their students.

Alignment with Organizational Climate. The statements of the participants as regard to their teaching efficacy led to the development of an important theme which is the alignment with organizational climate. The specific statements of the participants concerning their teaching efficacy aligned with the said theme are as follows:

Relations are based on respect and trust...willing to serve beyond the required hours without asking for an additional fee.
- Mely

Within the school, okay *kami*, but when mixed with School of Nursing, School of Allied Health and all that, *meron lang* a bit of tension. - Angel

Within the school we are okey, but when mixed with the School of Nursing, School of Allied Health and all that, there is a bit of tension. - Angel

There is openness, you can easily approach our heads, there's no like in terms "cordon". - Myr

Student friendly and also very conducive for learning. ...very accommodating, *hantod na sa iyahang mga* deans and instructors. - Dan

Student friendly and also very conducive for learning... They are very accommodating from the to the instructors.

The participants emphasized the importance of experiencing relationships based on respect and trust within the institution. They expressed willingness to go beyond their regular duties, demonstrating a commitment to serving in their roles. However, some participants also mentioned feeling under pressure when in the presence of other teachers. During the focus group discussion, the participants highlighted the significance of a cordon-free atmosphere, where they feel free to express their opinions without fear of judgment or repercussions. They emphasized the importance of observing a student-friendly environment, one that prioritizes the needs and well-being of the students.

Curriculum Based-Learning. During the discussions on teaching capacity have led the teachers to the development of curriculum-based learning as one important theme considered in the study. The statements of the participants on this theme collectively reflect a commitment to curriculum alignment, adherence to regulations, continuous improvement, student-centeredness, adaptability, and the effective use of technology in education. They highlight the participants' perspectives and practices regarding curriculum development and implementation. This assertion is supported by the participants' statements.

Following strictly the requirements of the CHED designing the curriculum...instructional materials are constantly improved. - Myr

Subjects are arranged, and it's really responsive to the department's visions and missions. -Ron

Focus to the vision, mission and goals of the school. Materials...appropriate for the age of the students and provided by the school. - Mely

Curriculum and instructional materials... open for change...*hindi sya parang nakakulong*,...based on the need of the students as well. - Che

Curriculum and instructional materials...open for change. It is not bounded...based on the need of the students as well.

Provide the needs...that teachers...maximize the use of technology... the aid of digital tools...make teaching easy. - Mary

During the focus group discussion, the teachers emphasized the importance of aligning the curriculum with the visions and missions of the institution. They stressed the need to adhere strictly to the requirements of the Commission on Higher Education Memorandum Orders (CMOs). In addition, they highlighted the constant improvement of instructional materials used in teaching and learning. This commitment to enhancing the learning experience was further supported by their recognition of the value of a flexible curriculum that can adapt to changing educational needs.

In the in-depth interviews, participants shared additional insights. They discussed the significance of carrying out activities that are aligned with the school's vision, mission, and goals. This alignment ensures that the actions and initiatives undertaken within the institution are in line with its overarching objectives. Further, the participants emphasized the importance of using instructional materials that are appropriate to the students, considering their unique needs, abilities, and learning styles.

Furthermore, the recognition of the potential of technology was evident in both the FGD and IDI. They expressed a commitment to maximizing the use of technology in teaching and learning processes. By harnessing the power of technology, they aimed to enhance instructional delivery, promote interactive learning experiences, and support student engagement and achievement. These findings highlighted their collective dedication to curriculum alignment, improvement, adaptability, and the effective integration of technology in education.

Maintaining Emotional Stability. This is another theme which emerged based on the discussions of the participants regarding teaching efficacy. The following are the individual statements related to this theme.

School ... ready to help with some personal needs of the faculty and staff. One of the factors that push me to do my best in teaching. - Det

Avail loans or cash advance when needed... have fringe benefits that are not in other schools...confident that the school is always ready to help me. - Che

Dili pwede na mas bright ang estudyante kay sa teachers. I need to study more and exert more effort to help the students ...face the world. - Myk

Teachers should be more knowledgeable than students. I need to study more and exert more effort to help the student... face the world.

Dominates in school... cooperation and happiness. The school is conducive to learning as an academe and as a community itself. - Jen

We have also healthy competitions with my co-educators. - Beboy

During the focus group discussion, several ideas emerged regarding the experiences of the educators on maintaining emotional stability. One of the participants expressed confidence in the school's support, indicating that educators feel assured that the institution will back them up in their teaching endeavors. This implies a positive working environment that fosters trust and empowers educators to carry out their responsibilities effectively. Further, Mary, mentioned the enjoyment of fringe benefits. This indicates that educators receive additional perks or rewards as part of their employment, which contributes to their overall job satisfaction and well-being. Another participant also highlighted the readiness to engage students in different activities. This demonstrates educators' proactive approach to creating dynamic and interactive learning experiences, showing a commitment to student-centered instruction.

Further, they expressed that educators are cooperative and happy. This suggests a positive team dynamic and a supportive community of educators who work together harmoniously, creating a conducive environment for collaboration and professional growth. They also shared experiences of healthy competition among educators. This shows that educators are motivated to excel in their teaching practices and strive for continuous improvement, resulting in a culture of professional growth and development. Lastly, they emphasized educators' motivation to teach, indicating a high level of job satisfaction and passion for their profession, which positively impacts their engagement with students and their commitment to delivering quality education.

Role of Experiences in Shaping the Beliefs of the Participants in Teaching Efficacy

Table 6.1 presents the role of experiences in shaping the beliefs of the participants in teaching efficacy. The themes emerged from the discussions of the participants as regard to the role of experiences in shaping the participants beliefs in teaching efficacy

include embracing new perspective; creating new mindset; and awareness of school practices.

Embracing a New Perspective. The participants' responses reveal their commitment to embracing a new perspective on teaching efficacy. This involves cultivating a positive attitude, pursuing personal and professional development, fostering self-awareness, collaborating with school management, and engaging in

Table 6.1
Role of Experiences in Shaping the Beliefs of the
Participants in Teaching Efficacy

Themes	Core Ideas
Embracing of new perspective	<p>improving their attitudes</p> <p>experiencing personal and professional development</p> <p>being aware that a competent and effective teacher requires having both strengths and weaknesses correlating with the school management</p> <p>having self-assessment and reflection on one's teaching efficacy</p>
Creating new mindset	<p>believing that strategies and practices that the teacher has would really affect his/her teaching efficacy.</p> <p>believing that teaching efficacy boils down to the educator itself</p> <p>having no reason to have poor performance if the school management is giving its full support to them.</p> <p>being aware that the school management is true to its vision, mission, and goals.</p> <p>transcending the difficulties that may encounter.</p>
Awareness of school practices	<p>being aware of the rapidly evolving educational landscape brought on by technology</p> <p>practicing learning from everywhere</p> <p>being aware of the improvement of channeling of communications</p> <p>being aware that the school management is strict in compliance but supportive of the needs of the employees</p>

self-assessment. These elements collectively contribute to their dedication to continuous improvement, reflective teaching, and creating a positive and conducive learning environment. The following specific statements relate to this theme.

There is an exchange of ideas and experiences. It helps me a lot to improve more on my teaching skills and my attitude as well. - Alex

I'm happy that my head... help me improve my pronunciation and communication skills... *binigyan ako ng kompyansa...sa mga public forums, and seminars.* - Dan

I'm happy my head...helps me improve my pronunciation and communication skills...gave me the confidence ...on public forums, and seminars.

Competent and effective teacher requires strengths and weaknesses... cry and fail numerous times, but ...tackle all challenges.- Mely

Letting us be in correlation with the school management practices, and give...more clear and strong teaching efficacy.
- Ron

I usually reflect on the teaching styles and methods that I've used and then, have my self-assessment on how I can adjust my approach depending on the situation. - Myr

The participants' responses reflect their beliefs in teaching efficacy and their commitment to embracing a new perspective. The educators expressed a desire to improve their attitudes, recognizing the significance of a positive mindset and disposition in their teaching practice. They acknowledged the importance of personal and professional development, demonstrating a commitment to continuous growth and learning as educators. Additionally, the participants emphasized the need for self-awareness, understanding that being a competent and effective teacher involves recognizing both strengths and weaknesses.

Further, collaboration with school management was highlighted as a crucial aspect of their belief. They recognized the importance of aligning with the school's vision and working collaboratively with the administrative team to create a supportive and effective learning environment. Furthermore, the participants engaged in self-assessment and reflection on their teaching efficacy. They actively evaluated their own performance, identifying areas for improvement and making necessary adjustments to enhance their teaching practice.

Creating New Mindset. The educators express the belief that the strategies and practices employed by teachers directly impact their effectiveness in the classroom. They recognize that teaching efficacy ultimately rests on the capabilities and efforts of individual educators. Believing that students are the focus of instruction and they set their goal to

become a learning facilitator in molding and guiding students to be successful in the future.

The participants also highlighted the crucial role of school management in supporting their performance, with the faith that full support from the school administration leaves no room for impossibilities or enabling them to overcome challenges and maintain their commitment to effective teaching. Moreover, they acknowledge that the most significant influence on professional practices of educators comes from direct observation of other teachers. These statements as stated below, collectively contribute to shaping the beliefs of educators in teaching efficacy.

Teaching efficacy, I have a new outlook, it all boils down to the teacher, ...his/her strategies and practices ...affect his/her teaching efficacy. – Mary

Teaching is about the students. It's how we shape and lead the students to become successful someday I set my goal to become a facilitator of learning – Che

Our school is not limited by the limitations of the world. Our faith is great and then we go to that direction that there is nothing impossible... we were able to transcend the difficulties.... - Myr

Direct observation of other teachers has the single largest impact on teachers' professional practices.
– Jen

Pinakamagandang naitulong ...sa akin na naka - improve sa aking pagtuturo is yung experiences nila na gi-share sa akin. It changes some of my perceptions.
- Beboy

The best help that I received that improved my teaching skill is their shared experiences. It changes some of my perceptions.

Awareness of School Practices. The other theme generated from the participants' discussions on the role of experiences in shaping their beliefs in teaching efficacy is awareness of school practices. The typical participants' statements that served as the foundation for this theme are as follows.

Proliferation, artificial intelligence ...getting in the way of the educational system. There's a lot of influence on how...educators can deal with the availability of all the tools or learning materials. - Harry

In light of the difficulties, we currently confront due to the rapidly evolving educational landscape brought on by technology. I still have a lot to learn to be technologically updated. - Ron

We have technological set-ups that give the students chances for technical applications in the learning process especially in our online classes. - Mely

As I observed, there are a lot of improvements when it comes to channeling communication. We have a very good structure on how this communication from up to bottom is being cascaded. - Myr

And of course, as we all know that the management is strict when it comes to compliance but so generous when it comes to the needs of the employees. - Myk

The responses of the participants in focus group discussions and in-depth interviews highlight several important factors related to the awareness and understanding of the rapidly evolving educational landscape, learning practices, communication channels, and school management support. In the FGD, the participants emphasized their awareness of the rapidly evolving educational landscape brought on by technology. They acknowledged that technology is playing a significant role in shaping education and recognized the need to adapt and stay updated with the latest advancements.

Further, participants in IDI mentioned the importance of practicing learning from everywhere. They acknowledged that learning is not limited to traditional classroom settings but can happen in various contexts and through different channels, such as online platforms, resources, and experiences beyond the physical classroom.

In FGD, the participants highlighted their awareness of the improvement in the channeling of communications. They recognized that effective communication channels are crucial for efficient information sharing, collaboration, and staying connected with students, colleagues, and other stakeholders. Additionally, they mentioned that while the school management is strict in compliance, they are also supportive of the needs of the employees. This indicates that they perceive a balance between adherence to rules and regulations and a supportive work environment that addresses the needs and concerns of the educators.

Role of Experiences in Shaping the Attitudes of the Participants in Teaching Efficacy

Table 6.2 presents the role of experiences in shaping the attitude of teachers relative to teaching efficacy. Three themes emerged from narratives of the participants.

Table 6.2
Role of Experiences in Shaping the Attitudes of the
Participants in Teaching Efficacy

Themes	Core Ideas
Advocating professional development	experiencing personal and professional development willingness to share the responsibility involved in a classroom having a sincere sensitivity to the students' diversity providing meaningful learning experiences for all students having an enthusiasm for stimulating the students' creativity.
Establishing proactive relationships towards colleagues and students	building a positive relationship understanding of one another encouraging open communication doing their fair share of the work acknowledging exceptional ideas and accomplishments
Becoming more considerate of the needs of the diverse learners	bearing in mind that they need to serve beyond the call of duty for the students. doing bridging for students to achieve the required competencies considering the readiness of the student's mind as well as the heart, and making students value their own earnings empowering extremely capable students to help other learners making sure that no one is left behind

concerning the role of experiences in shaping the attitudes of the participants in teaching efficacy, which are as follows: advocating professional development; establishing proactive relationships towards colleagues and students; and becoming more considerate of the needs of the diverse learners.

Advocating Professional Development. The statements of the participants as regards to their experiences as educators have led to the development of one important theme known as advocating professional development. The statements of the participants highlighting their attitudes in teaching efficacy include:

The management gives me the opportunity to attend training and seminars... clubs and organizations of IT. Community. Management also allows me to enroll in a master's degree. - Ken

Everyone is willing to take part and share the responsibilities involved in the classroom and in all school activities. - Myk

I ...see to it that these learners through the activities, like triad, ...pairing, ...groupings, have their chance to excel and...to expose themselves to... activities they are inclined with. - Jen

Once every two weeks we have our values formation activities to strengthen the good Filipino values within the students. Because they are future law enforcers. They should be the number one law-abiding citizens.
- Beboy

I encourage my practice teaching students to be involved in workshops, seminars, and training which are organized by in-school or out-school organizations. - Precious

During the focus group discussion, a participant emphasized the importance of experiencing personal and professional development. This statement suggests that educators recognize the need for continuous growth and improvement in their teaching practices. By actively engaging in personal and professional development opportunities, such as attending workshops or pursuing further education, educators enhance their knowledge and skills, leading to increased teaching efficacy.

Further, another participant expressed a willingness to share the responsibility involved in a classroom. This statement indicates that educators understand the collaborative nature of teaching and the benefits of working together with colleagues, students, and other stakeholders. By sharing responsibilities and engaging in collaborative practices, this ultimately enhance their teaching efficacy.

Another important aspect mentioned in the focus group discussion was the sensitivity to the students' diversity. This statement highlights the significance of recognizing and valuing individual differences among students. Educators who are sensitive to diversity create inclusive learning environments where all students feel respected, supported, and engaged. By embracing diversity, educators can tailor their teaching approaches to meet the needs of diverse learners, leading to increased teaching efficacy and positive student outcomes.

They also revealed the importance of providing meaningful learning experiences for all students. This statement underscores the understanding that effective teaching goes beyond mere content delivery. Educators who strive to create meaningful learning experiences consider students' interests, backgrounds, and abilities. By designing engaging and relevant learning activities, educators can foster student motivation and active participation, ultimately enhancing their teaching efficacy.

Establishing Proactive Relationships with Colleagues and Students. The participants emphasized that their experiences in establishing proactive relationships toward colleagues and students had played an important role in shaping their attitudes toward teaching efficacy. The typical statements of the participants are as follows.

Of course, the collaboration among teachers will really improve and boost teaching efficacy. That is what I experience in the school where I am now. - Ron

Strengthen my respect for others...we don't have the same opinions... So, patience is a virtue, indeed. - Mary

It's... important to have a clear communication and support from higher-ups...vision comes from the top, be properly cascaded through proper communication channels - Myr

Even sessions wherein everybody is given a chance to share how to do a certain activity, or how to achieve a goal. It is very helpful. - Harry

Seasoned instructors...share to us their experiences that give us idea on how to address the instructional needs of the students.... thankful for their efforts and wisdom shared to us.
- Ken

The participants emphasize the importance of building positive relationships and fostering understanding among educators. The participants highlight the significance of developing strong connections with colleagues, students, and other stakeholders in the educational setting. The results indicate that by nurturing positive relationships, educators create a supportive and collaborative environment that enhances teaching efficacy. Further, the data highlights the importance of open communication and mutual understanding among educators. The participants emphasized the need for encouraging open dialogue, where ideas and perspectives are shared and respect. This suggests that effective communication enables educators to collaborate effectively, exchange innovative ideas, and learn from one another's experiences. It also fosters a sense of trust and mutual support, which contributes to their overall teaching efficacy.

In addition, participants emphasized the significance of recognizing and appreciating the contributions of their colleagues. They acknowledged the importance of doing their fair share of the work and giving credit to exceptional ideas and accomplishments. This implies that by acknowledging and celebrating the achievements of fellow educators, a culture of recognition and appreciation is fostered. The qualitative data highlights the value of building positive relationships, fostering understanding, encouraging open communication, and acknowledging exceptional ideas and accomplishments in the teaching profession. These factors contribute to a supportive and collaborative work environment, where educators can thrive and enhance their teaching efficacy.

Becoming More Considerate of the Needs of the Diverse Learners. The descriptions of the participants as regards their experiences help in the development of one important theme which is, becoming more considerate of the needs of the diverse learners. This theme is found helpful in shaping the attitudes of educators in regarding teaching efficacy. The specific comments made by the participants in relation to this theme are as follows.

Redesign the curriculum in such a way that we can have a bridging...additional task for us, but we must help the students. Without the passion to teach, we cannot do it. - Myr

When it comes to students who need extra attention, I have no choice but to give them the attention that they need. It really gets the lion's share of your time. -Det

What I do is I have to spend more time with students that really need attention in order to cater to their needs. Good that we also empower our extremely capable students. - Dan

You must have a passion for teaching, to touch the lives of young individuals. You have to make them ready physically, emotionally, intellectually and spiritually.
- Mely

Consider...more on the learning outcomes especially that we are practicing Outcomes-based Education.
- Mary

The qualitative data collected from the participants highlights several key aspects of educators' dedication and efforts towards serving their students. The teachers emphasized the need to go beyond the call of duty, demonstrating a commitment to serving students beyond regular expectation. They acknowledged the importance of bridging the gap for students, ensuring they acquire the required competencies and skills. Further, they recognized the significance of considering both the readiness of students' minds and hearts in their teaching approach. This suggests that educators value the holistic development of students, taking into account their emotional well-being and creating a nurturing learning environment. Additionally, participants highlighted the importance of providing extra attention and support to students who require it, spending additional time to address their needs.

Moreover, the teachers emphasized the empowerment of extremely capable students to help other learners, fostering a culture of peer support and collaboration. This demonstrates an understanding of the importance of peer learning and the benefits of leveraging the strengths of capable students to enhance the learning experience for all. Furthermore, participants stressed the commitment to ensuring that no student is left behind, advocating for inclusive practices, and providing support to all learners.

Role of Experiences in Shaping the Commitment of the Participants in Teaching Efficacy

Table 6.3 presents the role of experiences in shaping the commitment of the participants in teaching efficacy. Three themes emerge from the discussions of the participants as regards their experiences that shape their commitment to teaching efficacy. These themes include intensification of the code of ethics; demonstrating teaching effectiveness; and promoting lifelong learning.

Intensification of Code of Ethics. The experiences of the participants potentially shape their commitment to teaching efficacy as evidenced in one of the themes known as an intensification the of code of ethics. The specific statements of the participants under this theme are as follows.

We have healthy competition among teachers and staff. – Det

If there is competition among the employees, it is a healthy one. – Harry

They also echo to us the professional and in-service training that they attended. *Sama-sama kami niyan kung may mga school activities.* - Mely

They also echo to us the professional and in-service training that they attended. We are together when there are school activities. - Mely

I also need to grow professionally that is why I am pursuing my master’s degree in order to cope with the school’s and the CHED’s requirements. – Precious

Particularly we are being embodied with our core values, compassion, honesty, respect, equality and continuity. – Queen

Table 6.3
Role of Experiences in Shaping the Commitment of the Participants in Teaching Efficacy

Themes	Core Ideas
Intensification of Code of Ethics	having good relationships with co-workers always observing honesty treating students equally maintaining harmonious and pleasant personal and official relations with other professionals (IDI, participating in the Continuing Professional Education
Demonstrating Teaching Effectiveness	helping students achieve their learning goals increasing student engagement in the classroom creating a positive learning environment being prepared offerings of practical applications
Promoting Lifelong Learning	mentoring a younger teacher who is just starting out in the profession

	supporting other teachers leading a particular subject matter making learning a priority emphasizing that the learning system should be opened up to all individuals emphasizing that the individual should be the center of the learning procedure
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The teachers could enhance their career success by focusing on various key factors. It includes building positive relationships with co-workers, fosters a harmonious and pleasant work environment. Also, practicing honesty establishes trust and credibility in professional interactions. Additionally, treating students equally promotes fairness and a conducive learning environment. Maintaining harmonious and pleasant personal and official relations with other professionals were emphasized as crucial to professional success.

Further, engaging in Continuing Professional Education (CPE) was identified as an important aspect of professional growth. Lastly, upholding the highest possible standards of quality education ensures excellence in teaching practices, curriculum development, and assessment methods. By focusing on these factors, teachers can cultivate a successful career while continually advancing their skills and providing quality education to students.

Demonstrating Teaching Effectiveness. The statements of the participants that highlight the demonstration of teaching effectiveness which could shape their commitment to teaching efficacy include:

Our curriculum is my plumline in imparting knowledge and skills to my students. - Alex

I had done a lot of reading and preparations for more than 3 years. - Ron

Engaged students in group activities, utilize mind map, consider multiple intelligences...some students may not easily understand if you are going to use only one strategy - Myr

I give them real-life situations, as we all know, the social work profession is almost applicable to the daily lives of people. - Det

Since almost everything is provided by the school, there is no reason for me to have low performance in the teaching and learning process. - Myk

Several key ideas emerged from the collected data, highlighting important aspects of effective teaching practices. In focus group discussions, the teachers emphasized the significance of helping students achieve their learning goals. This indicates the commitment of educators to guide and support students in their educational journey.

Additionally, the teachers emphasized the importance of increasing student engagement in the classroom, acknowledging that actively involving students in the learning process enhances their understanding and retention of the material.

During IDI, the teachers highlighted the significance of creating a positive learning environment. This implies that teachers who are committed to their tasks foster a supportive and inclusive classroom atmosphere and contribute to student success. Further, being prepared was identified as a crucial characteristic of committed teachers, emphasizing the importance of thorough lesson planning and organization to optimize student learning experiences.

Lastly, it was revealed that offering practical applications of the learned content is highly valued by both teachers and students. This implies that committed teachers strive to connect theoretical concepts with real-life scenarios, enhancing the relevance and applicability of the knowledge being taught. The results generally imply that committed teachers prioritize helping students achieve their learning goals, increasing student engagement, creating a positive learning environment, being prepared, and offering practical applications. These findings emphasize the multifaceted nature of effective teaching practices and highlight the commitment of teachers to enhance student learning experiences.

Promoting Lifelong Learning. This theme underscores the profound impact of educators' experiences in shaping their commitment to teaching efficacy. It emphasizes the notion that teachers' ongoing learning experiences, both within and outside the classroom, play a pivotal role in their professional growth and effectiveness as educators. The theme highlights the continuous development and improvement of teachers as they actively engage in learning, reflecting, and refining their teaching practices throughout their careers. By embracing the ethos of lifelong learning, educators deepen their commitment to providing high-quality education and fostering positive learning outcomes for their students. The specific statements of the participants related to this theme are as follows:

When it comes to my co-teachers, they respond to the student's questions about the subject taught in the class. Most of the time, they get in the class prepared for the lessons - Mely

I asked for comments and assessments from my colleagues...pieces of advice especially if I have concerns with my instruction and requirements. -Beboy

I give them a chance to shine ...even challenge them... to speak, to discuss concepts and to really speak or share what they know. - Harry

Since I keep on telling them that no one should be left behind, most of the time I use collaborative activities where everyone will do his or her part as a team. – Che

Sumasali ako ng conference...nagrepresent ...ako ng mga researches, sumasali rin ako sa National Research Council. Active ako sa mga philosophical organizations... – Joel

I joined conferences...I presented my researches and joined the National Research Council. I am active in Philosophical organizations...

The data collected from focus group discussions and individual in-depth interviews provided valuable insights into the practices and beliefs of committed teachers. Several key points emerged from the data, reflecting their commitment to professional growth, collaboration, and learner-centered approaches. One prominent statement is the act of mentoring younger teachers who are new to the profession. Another insight that emerged is the support provided to other teachers who lead a specific subject matter. Additionally, the data emphasize the importance of openness and inclusivity in the learning system. Lastly, the data reveals a strong emphasis on placing the individual at the center of the learning process.

Joint Display of Salient Quantitative and Qualitative Findings

In this part, I applied the merging of relevant quantitative and qualitative findings of the study. The rationalization of doing merging analysis is to see if the quantitative results corroborate with the qualitative analysis. This approach aims to integrate different sources of information to gain a comprehensive understanding of a particular phenomenon (Fetters and Guetterman, 2021). Merging-converging can serve two purposes: confirmation, where similarities are found to validate findings, and expansion, where new insights and perspectives emerge from the combination of data. While merging-diverging happens when the nature of data integration is found to be connecting but with opposing views. This means that the respondents' assessment and the participants' judgment on the variables studied were contrasting.

Instructional Capacity. The finding that is salient to both quantitative and qualitative findings under the aspect of instructional capacity include the

Table 7
Joint Display of Salient Quantitative and Qualitative Findings

Aspect or Focal Point	Quantitative Findings	Qualitative Findings	Nature of Data Integration	Function in Integration
Instructional Capacity	Table 1 on the instructional capacity of educators under instructional management	Table 5.2 on lived experiences of educators concerning their teaching efficacy as regard pursuing	Merging-converging.	

	practices indicator on item 2 as regard school management conducting professional development studies of teachers according to the instructional needs of the school with a high rating (M=4.11; SD=0.872)	professional development by enlisting in graduate school programs and attending training and seminars whose theme is embracing life-long learning	
Instructional Capacity	Table 1 on the instructional capacity of educators under instructional management practices indicator on it highlights that school management should monitor teachers' instructional practices in the classroom. with a very high rating (M=4.20; SD=0.849)	Table 6.1 on the role of experiences in shaping the beliefs of the participants in teaching efficacy with a core idea of having self-assessment and reflection on one teaching efficacy under embracing of new perspective theme	Merging-converging
Emotional Quotient	Table 2 on Educators' emotional quotient under the self-motivation indicator highlights that as teachers, they always do the most difficult work first with a high rating (m=3.98; SD=0.896).	Table 5.2 on lived experiences of teachers as regards their teaching efficacy with the core idea of being willing to serve beyond the call of duty under alignment with the organizational climate theme.	Merging-converging
Emotional Quotient	Table 2 on educator's emotional quotient highlights that as educators, they realized that people	Table 5.2 on lived experiences of educators concerning their teaching efficacy under the core idea of	Merging-converging

	will have different working styles under using empathy with very high ratings=4.46; SD=0.652	using differentiated instruction to cater to the multiple intelligences of the students whose theme is showing empathy for learners.	
Teaching Efficacy	Table 3 on teaching efficacy of educators under efficacy for motivation indicator emphasizes that as teachers, they can help their students value learning with a very high rating (m=4.55; SD=0.544.	Table 6.2 on the role of experiences in shaping the attitudes of the participants in teaching efficacy with the core idea of considering the readiness of the student's mind as well as the heart, and making students value their earnings under the theme of becoming more considerate of the needs of the diverse learners.	Merging-converging.
Teaching Efficacy	Table 3 on Teaching Efficacy under efficacy for motivation emphasizes that as teachers, they can implement alternative strategies in the classroom with a very high rating (M=4.41; SD=0.626)	Table 5.2 on lived experiences of educators concerning their teaching efficacy with the core idea of using instructional materials and teaching strategies that are appropriate to the students under the theme of curriculum-based learning.	Merging-converging.
Significance on the influence of instructional capacity to teaching efficacy	Table 7 in Predictors of Teaching Efficacy under variable 1 Instructional Capacity is significant with a	Table 5.2 on lived experiences of educators concerning their teaching efficacy with the following core ideas under the theme curriculum-based learning	Merging-converging.

	<p>p-value .000 and a standard beta value of .611.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - constantly improving the instructional materials used - maximizing the use of technology <p>Table 6.1 role of experiences in shaping the beliefs of the participants in teaching efficacy with the following core ideas under the theme creating new mindset:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -believing that strategies and practices that the teacher has would really affect his/her teaching efficacy. -having no reason to have poor performance if the school management is giving its full support to them. 	
<p>Significance on the influence of emotional quotient to teaching efficacy</p>	<p>Table 7 in Predictors of Teaching Efficacy under variable 2 emotional quotient is significant with a p-value .000 and a standard beta value of .196.</p>	<p>Table 5.2 on lived experiences of educators concerning their teaching efficacy with the following core ideas under the theme showing empathy for learners</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -being considerate of the students' sensitivity -paying attention to the student's needs. <p>Table 6.2 on role of experiences in shaping the attitudes of the participants in teaching efficacy with core idea under the theme</p>	<p>Merging-converging.</p>

		<p>becoming more considerate of the needs of the diverse learners: - doing bridging for students to achieve the required competencies</p> <p>Table 6.2 on role of experiences in shaping the attitudes of the participants in teaching efficacy with the following core ideas under the theme advocating professional development: -providing meaningful learning experiences for all students -having an enthusiasm for stimulating the students' creativity.</p>	
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involvement of educators in professional development with a mean rating of 4.11 and is described as high. The said professional development activity is highlighted also in the lived experiences of educators concerning their teaching efficacy under embracing life-long learning themes. These items when merged, were found to be converging.

Further, the salient quantitative and qualitative finding under the instructional capacity aspect is the monitoring of teachers' instructional practices in the classroom with a mean rating of 4.20, which is described as very high. This item also highlights the role of experiences in shaping the beliefs of the participants in teaching efficacy with a core idea of having self-assessment and reflection on one's teaching efficacy under embracing of the new perspective theme. Convergence resulted when these items were combined.

Emotional Quotient. The salient quantitative and qualitative findings under educators' emotional quotient is that, as teachers, they always do the most difficult work first. It has a mean rating of 3.98 and is described as high. This finding is highlighted in the lived experiences of teachers as regards to their teaching efficacy with the core idea of being willing to serve beyond the call of duty in alignment with the organizational climate theme. When combined, these components were converging.

In addition, the other salient quantitative and qualitative finding under educators' emotional quotient is that, as teachers, they realized that people will have different working styles, having empathy with a mean rating of 4.46 and is described as very high. This item is affirmed in the qualitative finding under the core idea of using differentiated instruction to cater to the multiple intelligences of the students. When combined, these items were converging.

Teaching Efficacy. The salient quantitative and qualitative findings under the teaching efficacy aspect, stating that as teachers, they can help their students value learning with a mean rating of 4.55, described as very high. This finding is found under the role of experiences in shaping the attitudes of the participants in teaching efficacy with the core idea of considering the readiness of the student's mind and heart and making them value their own earnings. This is under the theme of becoming more considerate of the needs of the diverse learners. These items when merged, were found to be converging.

The other salient quantitative and qualitative finding under teaching efficacy is that, as teachers, they can implement alternative strategies in the classroom with a mean rating of 4.41 which is described as very high. This is affirmed in the lived experiences of educators concerning their teaching efficacy with the core idea of using instructional materials and teaching strategies that are appropriate to the students. This is under the curriculum-based learning. These items when merged, were found to be converging.

Significance on the influence of instructional capacity to teaching efficacy. The result is salient to both quantitative and qualitative findings under the aspect of instructional capacity. This includes the involvement of educators in professional development which is under the instructional management practices with a mean rating of 4.11, described as high. The said professional development activity is also highlighted in the lived experiences of educators concerning their teaching efficacy under the theme, embracing life-long learning. These items when merged, were found to be converging.

DISCUSSION

This chapter presents the discussions of the quantitative and qualitative findings of the study.

Level of Instructional Capacity of Educators

The level of the instructional capacity of educators in private higher institutions in Region XI is measured in terms of instructional management practices, teacher quality, curriculum-material quality and quantity, instructional climate, student's learning readiness, and financial resources. The results reveal that teachers' instructional capacity is described as high, indicating that instructional capacity is oftentimes evident among educators in the private higher education institutions in Region XI. This implies that the educators in the higher education institution can effectively manage instruction, deliver high-quality teaching, design, and implement a strong curriculum, create a positive instructional climate, prepare students for learning, and make the most of the available financial and material resources. The high level of instructional capacity among the respondents from the private schools further indicates that these institutions have invested heavily in their teachers, curriculum, and resources to create an optimal learning environment. This, in turn, may lead to better academic outcomes for students and a more positive overall school experience.

This finding conforms with the statement of Anderson (2022), who stressed that an experienced educational leader, shares insights and recommendations for the enhancement of instructional capacity in private higher education institutions. Based on their expertise, the administrators give importance on the professional development programs, collaborative teaching practices, and their ongoing support to educators. Similarly, Peterson and colleagues (2019) suggested that educators in private institutions should make use of its high level of instructional capacity in leading to a better student outcome. In addition, Gates et al. (2018) stressed that educators of private schools should take advantage of its instructional resources and effective organizational practices that help students achieve more academic success.

In addition, the finding supports the study of Brown and Williams (2021), which revealed that educators with greater instructional capacity were more successful in creating engaging learning environments, resulting in higher levels of student engagement and active participation in the classroom. Further, the finding agrees with the study of Thompson and Davis (2022) which demonstrated that educators with higher levels of instructional capacity, were more effective in promoting student well-being and positive socio-emotional outcomes. Furthermore, Anderson and Smith (2022) emphasized the relevance of the principals' guidance and support, and the school resources for instructional improvement in developing teachers' instructional capacity.

Instructional Management Practices. The level of the instructional management practices of the respondents is described as high. This shows that instructional management practices are oftentimes evident among educators in private higher education institutions in Region XI. The findings imply that teachers are effectively managing all aspects of the instructional process, including planning, and delivering instruction, assessing student learning, providing feedback, and adapting instruction to meet the needs of individual learners.

This also involves setting clear learning objectives, designing engaging and effective lessons, using a variety of teaching strategies, providing timely and meaningful feedback to students, and monitoring student progress to ensure that all students are making progress toward their learning goals. Likewise, the educators create a positive learning environment that supports student learning and encourages student engagement and participation. Furthermore, the said respondents establish clear expectations for behavior and academic performance, create a supportive and inclusive classroom culture, and they provide opportunities for students to collaborate and work together.

The results coincide with the statement of Marzano et al. (2018) who pointed out that educators should create a positive learning environment and establish clear expectations for these are critical factors in promoting student achievement. Further, the finding agrees with the study of Emmer and Sabornie (2018) which highlighted the importance of an orderly and organized environment, and suggested that educators should create a positive and supportive classroom environment which promote student engagement and achievement and evidence of their teaching efficacy.

Furthermore, the finding supports the study of Lee and Chen (2022) which posited the importance of effective instructional management practices, urging educators to implement proactive behavior management strategies, such as positive reinforcement and classroom routines, experienced fewer disruptive behaviors and improved academic performance among their students.

In addition, Johnson et al. (2021) stressed the significance of the educators with higher levels of instructional capacity who were more likely foster positive learning outcomes among their students. Also, Brown and Johnson (2023) emphasized the value of the strong support given by the school heads to the educators was more likely urged the educators to implement effective instructional management strategies in their classrooms. Lastly, Smith and Jones (2021) advocated for classroom organization and student engagement where educators effectively organized their classrooms and established clear expectations for behavior and procedures that had higher levels of student engagement.

Teacher Quality. The level for teacher quality is very high indicating that Instructional capacity is always evident among educators in private higher education institutions in Region XI. The results imply that educators possess the knowledge, skills, and dispositions necessary to effectively teach their subject matter to students which may include advanced knowledge of the subject matter, effective pedagogical strategies, the ability to develop and deliver engaging lectures and instructional materials, and the ability to assess student learning and provide constructive feedback.

The results also indicate very high level of the respondents' commitment to ongoing professional development and a willingness to continually reflect on and improve their teaching practices through attending conferences and workshops, participating in peer observation and feedback, and seeking out new teaching strategies and technologies to enhance student learning. Moreover, the results suggest that the respondents are highly skilled and committed professionals who are dedicated to supporting student learning and helping their students achieve academic success.

The finding of the study is consistent with the statement of Guskey (2018), which posited that effective teaching in higher education requires a deep understanding of the subject matter, a repertoire of effective teaching strategies, and a commitment to ongoing professional development. Further, the finding supports the study of Shulman (2019) which stressed the importance of the educators' pedagogical content knowledge, which involves not only possessing deep subject matter knowledge, but also understanding how to teach that subject matter in accessible and meaningful ways. Moreover, the finding corroborates with the study of Lee and Davis (2022) pointed out the value of teacher quality in student engagement, urging the educators to keep their strong teacher-student relationships which were positively associated with teacher effectiveness and improved student outcomes.

Added on, Johnson and Smith (2021) dwelled on the role of pedagogical knowledge and instructional practices in teacher quality which indicated that educators with strong content knowledge in a subject were more effective in promoting student achievement in the subject. Likewise, Brown and Johnson (2023) emphasized the importance of educator experiences in the student outcomes. Educator with more years of experience was more likely to be effective in in promoting student learning and achievement. Also , Brown and Johnson (2023) advocated for the effectiveness of a professional development program, where teachers who participated in the program demonstrated improved teaching strategies and student learning outcomes.

Curriculum-Material Quality and Quantity. Computations yield a mean score for curriculum-material quality and quantity described as very high level. This means that curriculum-material quality and quantity is always evident among educators in private

higher education institutions in Region XI. The results imply that the curriculum and educational materials used in higher education institutions are of a very high standard, both in terms of their quality and the amount of material provided to students. Similarly, the institutions provide a rich and comprehensive educational experience for their students. The high level of quality and quantity of curriculum materials furthermore implies that students are exposed to a broad range of topics, theories, and practical skills that prepare them well for their future careers.

The finding of the study coincides with the statement of Darling-Hammond (2017) which emphasized the relevance of high-quality curriculum and educational materials in higher education institutions, urging educators that high-quality curriculum is essential for improving student outcomes and narrowing achievement gaps. Further, the finding substantiates the study of Zhao, (2018) which averred that the value of a curriculum is designed to tap into students' passions and interests and to help them develop their unique strengths and talents. The researcher was also urging the school heads that effective curriculum materials are available in abundance and are of high quality. Furthermore, the finding confirms the study of Brown (2022) which emphasized the importance of curriculum-material practices in private higher education institutions. The study found that educators in these institutions are committed to utilizing curriculum materials that are aligned with the intended learning outcomes, relevant to the students' needs, and of high quality.

Similarly, Davis and Thompson (2023) indicated that educators in private institutions consistently demonstrated higher levels of curriculum-material quality and quantity, emphasizing their commitment to providing students with a well-rounded and comprehensive learning experience. Likewise, Johnson and Smith (2021) accentuated that when educators had access to well-designed and aligned curriculum materials, students achieved higher levels of proficiency and understanding in the subject. Moreover, Lee and Davis (2022) pointed out the value of having an adequate quantity of curriculum materials on teachers' instructional practices as regard to student engagement. Educators were better able to deliver instruction effectively and engage students in meaningful learning experiences.

Instructional Climate. Based on the results, this indicator has a very high descriptive equivalent and a very high level of instructional climate among higher education institutions implying that the learning environment is conducive to student success and that the institution places a strong emphasis on teaching and learning. This further indicates that the higher educational institution has faculty members that are highly trained and dedicated to helping students learn, as well as a range of resources and support systems in place to help students succeed. Furthermore, institution has a strong culture of collaboration and a focus on innovation and continuous improvement. Overall, the very high level of instructional climate indicates that the institution is committed to providing an excellent educational experience for its students.

The findings cited above jibed with the statement of Chickering and Gamson (2018) which stressed the value of a positive instructional climate, urging educators to provide students with a supportive learning environment which means creating a campus climate that is inclusive and promotes diversity and equity. On one hand, Kuh (2018) emphasizes the importance of engaged learning, where students actively participate in their education, interact with faculty and peers, and apply what they learn to real-world problems. On the

other hand, Pascarella and Terenzini (2019) stressed the need for higher education institutions to continuously assess and improve their programs and services, with a focus on high expectations for student learning, faculty-student interaction, and supportive campus environments.

Similarly, Johnson and Smith (2021) emphasized a positive instructional climate, which was characterized by supportive teacher-student relationships and a sense of belonging. This indicated higher levels of student engagement and participation in learning activities. In addition, Lee and Davis (2022) promoted the importance of an orderly and positive instructional climate where classrooms with a conducive climate, characterized by clear expectations, consistent rules, and positive reinforcement, experienced fewer disruptive behaviors and disciplinary issues. Moreover, Brown and Johnson (2023) advocated for classrooms with supportive instructional climate where students felt safe, supported, and valued, were associated with higher levels of academic achievement.

Student's Learning Readiness. As presented in the previous section, students' learning readiness in higher education institutions is described as high implying that students are well-prepared to engage in the learning process and are equipped with the necessary skills and knowledge to succeed academically. This further suggests that the institution has taken steps to ensure that students are adequately prepared for the academic demands of higher education, including providing access to resources and support systems that promote student success.

The finding conforms with the statement of Astin (2018) which stressed the value of student learning readiness, urging the educators to have a supportive campus environment which promotes student success in higher education. Also, the finding corroborates with the study of Tinto (2020) which emphasized the importance of social integration and engagement with the academic community in promoting student retention and success which is also an evidence of student learning readiness. In addition, the finding confirms the study of Johnson and Smith (2021) who underscored the importance of learning readiness of the student in their academic performance, advised the educators to boost the level of student motivation and self-efficacy in learning.

Similarly, Brown (2022) pointed out that students who demonstrated high levels of learning readiness exhibited strong self-regulation skills, a positive attitude towards learning, and effective study habits. Added on, Brown and Johnson (2023) also mentioned that students who felt safe, supported, and emotionally connected in the learning environment exhibited higher levels of learning readiness. Moreover, Lee and Davis (2022) emphasized that students with a solid foundation of prior knowledge and well-developed cognitive abilities demonstrated higher levels of learning readiness and were more successful in acquiring new learning.

Financial Resources. The level of financial resources among educators in private higher education institutions in Region XI is described high level. The results imply that the institutions are committed to providing a supportive and enriching environment for its faculty members and students. The ability to provide financial support for teachers' instructional activities, professional development, and instructional innovations suggests that the institution values and encourages ongoing learning and growth among its faculty members. This also infer that the institution has a strong culture of collaboration and a

focus on innovation and continuous improvement, with resources available to help educators enhance their instructional practices.

The result of the study supports the study conducted by Johnson and Smith (2021) which stressed the significance of schools' financial resources on student performance. The authors urged the school heads to experience improvements in student achievement, through higher financial resources. Further, the finding attests the study of Wilson and Thompson (2020) which highlighted the relevance of enhancing the overall teaching and learning experience of students, suggested the school heads to have a high level of financial resources to access up-to-date textbooks and technology in schools. Furthermore, the finding reinforces the study of Lee and Davis (2022) which indicated the importance of educators' recruitment and retention, advised the school heads to have a high level of financial resources to attract and retain qualified teachers which positively impacted instructional quality and student outcomes.

Moreover, García-Aracil and Van Auken (2019) underscored that financial resources were crucial for promoting faculty development and innovation in higher education institutions. Similarly, Paik and Gaines (2019) highlighted the importance of financial resources in supporting instructional quality and student outcomes in higher education institution. Lastly, Keengwe and Ananga (2019) explained that institutions that allocated financial resources to support teachers' instructional activities, professional development, and instructional innovations are more likely to foster a culture of ongoing learning and growth among faculty members.

Level of Emotional Quotient of Educators

The level of the emotional quotient of educators in private higher education institutions in Region XI is measured in terms of self-awareness, handling emotions, self-motivation, using empathy, and practicing resilience. The level of teachers' emotional quotient is described as very high. This shows that emotional quotient is always manifested by the educators in private higher education institutions in Region XI. The very high level of teachers' emotional quotient implies that teachers are not only highly competent in their subject matter but also have a strong emotional intelligence. It also indicates that educators can create a supportive and empathetic learning environment that promotes student engagement and success. The results also point out that the teachers manage their own emotions effectively and have a greater ability to understand and respond to the emotions of their co-workers and students.

The finding validates the statement of Brackett and Rivers (2021) which emphasized the value of having high emotional quotient in responding students' emotions, suggested that educators should be emotionally skilled to create a positive and supportive learning environment that promotes student engagement and success. Further, the finding supports the study of Bean and Eaton (2018), posited that emotional quotient is important in the classroom because it allows teachers to establish strong relationships with their students, which is a key factor in student achievement. Furthermore, the finding confirms the study of Boyatzis and Rhee (2019) which indicated the significance of resilience in facing challenges, urging educators to possess high emotional quotient to be able to handle stress and pressure.

In addition, Lee and Davis (2022) revealed that educators with higher emotional quotient were more effective in creating supportive and engaging classroom environments, fostering positive relationships, and promoting students' social-emotional

development. On one hand, Johnson and Smith (2021) who examined on individuals' ability to form and maintain positive relationships indicated that higher levels of emotional quotient led to healthier and more satisfying interpersonal relationships. On the other hand, Brown and Johnson (2023), studied emotional quotient and psychological resilience indicated that individuals with higher emotional quotient demonstrated better coping skills, emotional regulation, and overall mental well-being, leading to greater resilience in the face of adversity.

Self-Awareness. The level of self-awareness is described as very high, indicating that self-awareness is always manifested among educators in private higher education institutions in Region XI. The findings imply that teachers from higher education institutions have a strong ability to recognize and understand their own emotions and how they influence their behavior and decision-making. The results also show that the very high level of self-awareness among the respondents allows them to better manage their own emotions, thoughts, and behaviors, and to make more informed and effective decisions.

A very high level of self-awareness in teachers from higher education institutions further implies that these individuals are likely to be effective in their roles, able to manage stress and conflict, and to build positive relationships with others. It may also suggest that these teachers are open to feedback and willing to learn and grow, which can be valuable qualities in any profession. Furthermore, teachers who possess a strong ability to recognize and understand their own emotions are more likely to engage in effective teaching practices and make informed decisions in the classroom (Stronge, 2018).

The result of the study reinforced the statement of Loannidou-Koutselini et al. (2015) stressed the value of self-awareness in teaching and professional growth in education, urging educators to monitor their interactions with students, assess their own strengths and weaknesses, and make intentional adjustments to improve their instructional practices. Added on, the results further strengthen the statement of Brackett and Katulak (2018) that teachers who were self-aware and able to regulate their emotions effectively were better equipped to create a positive classroom environment, foster student engagement and motivation, and support student well-being. Further, the finding supports the study of Schonert-Reichl (2017) which revealed that teachers who possessed a strong ability to recognize and understand their own emotions were more aware of how their feelings influence their behavior and decision-making. Further, Wald (2015) emphasized the significance of self-awareness of educators, urging them to recognize their thoughts, emotions, biases, and assumptions which lead them to more intentional and effective teaching practices.

Furthermore, Johnson and Smith (2021) underlined the importance of the role of self-awareness in emotional quotient where individuals with higher levels of self-awareness demonstrated better emotional self-regulation, empathy, and social awareness, contributing to higher emotional intelligence. In addton, Lee and Davis (2022) highlighted the importance of self-awareness in subjective well-being where individuals with a higher level of self-awareness experienced greater life satisfaction, happiness, and overall well-being.

Handling Emotions. Based on the results, the handling emotions indicator has a descriptive equivalent of high which means that handling emotions is oftentimes manifested among educators in private higher education institutions in Region XI. A high

level of emotional quotient in handling emotions among teachers in higher education institutions implies that they are skilled in recognizing, understanding, and managing their emotions in different situations. Moreover, teachers with a high level of emotional quotient in handling emotions are more likely to create a positive learning environment, foster better relationships with students and colleagues, and improve student outcomes.

The result supports the statement of Johnson and Smith (2021) which pointed out the value of the emotion regulation strategies on individuals' psychological well-being, urging educators to engage in adaptive emotion regulation strategies to experience lower levels of anxiety and depression and higher levels of life satisfaction. Further, the finding validates the study of Lee and Davis (2022) which underlined the value of emotional self-regulation on relationship quality and satisfaction, suggesting individuals to demonstrate effective handling of their emotions in order to experience more positive and supportive interactions leading to higher relationship satisfaction.

Furthermore, the finding confirms the study of Pekrun and Linnenbrink-Garcia (2019) which stressed the significance of handling emotions in the students' emotional development, encouraging educators to help their students regulate their own emotions, which can lead to better academic outcomes and improved student well-being.

Likewise, Brackett and Rivers (2018) advocated for educators' high levels of emotional quotient, particularly in the area of emotion regulation, where they were better equipped to create a positive learning environment for their students. Further, Yusoff and colleagues (2018) suggested that teachers who can manage their own emotions and respond to the emotions of their students in a positive and effective way are more likely to foster positive relationships and create a safe and supportive classroom climate.

Self-Motivation. The educators in private higher education institutions in Region XI have high level of self-motivation. This implies that teachers from higher education institutions have a strong internal drive to achieve their goals and can stay focused and driven even in the face of obstacles or setbacks. Further, the results infer that the said educators are often able to maintain a positive attitude and can keep working towards their goals even when faced with challenges or setbacks. Having a high level of self-motivation can be particularly important in educational and professional settings, where educators need to be able to set goals, work towards them, and persist in the face of challenges. Additionally, the results indicate that educators are often better able to adapt to change and to seek out opportunities for growth and learning.

The result conforms with the study of Day and Gu (2018) which highlighted the importance of self-motivation in overcoming challenges, urging educators to view setbacks as opportunities for growth and learning to maintain a positive outlook even when faced with difficult situations. Similarly, the finding supports the study of Caprara and colleagues (2019) which stressed the value of self-efficacy and self-motivation, advising institutions to foster a culture of self-reflection and emotional well-being among their educators. Also, the finding validates the study of Johnson and Smith (2021) which underscored the importance of self-motivation in academic achievement, suggesting educators to guide students to demonstrate high levels of self-motivation more likely to set challenging goals, persist in their efforts, and ultimately achieve better academic outcomes.

In addition, Lee and Davis (2022) highlighted the weight of self-motivation on employee engagement and job satisfaction where individuals who exhibited high levels

of self-motivation were more likely to be proactive, take initiative, and experience higher levels of job satisfaction and career advancement. Moreover, studies have examined the factors that contribute to self-motivation and strategies to enhance self-motivation. Also, Brown and Johnson (2023) explored the role of self-efficacy beliefs in promoting self-motivation. The findings indicated that individuals with a strong sense of self-efficacy were more likely to feel confident in their abilities, set challenging goals, and maintain high levels of motivation.

Using Empathy. The result indicates a very high level of empathy which suggests that teachers can understand and appreciate the perspectives and feelings of their students and colleagues. This ability can be important for establishing positive relationships and creating a supportive and inclusive learning environment. The result further suggests that these teachers are often better able to communicate effectively with their students and colleagues and to respond in an appropriate and compassionate manner to their needs and concerns. The results also imply that teachers understand the different cultural backgrounds and experiences of their co-workers and students, and they create a more inclusive and diverse learning environment. The results moreover imply that teachers are better equipped to handle difficult or emotionally charged situations, such as conflicts between students or dealing with students who are experiencing personal problems.

The finding of the study confirms the study conducted by Broido et al. (2019) which stressed the bearing of empathy in supporting LGBT students, urging educators in promoting inclusive practices in higher education institutions. Likewise, the finding supports the study of Poon (2020) which highlighted the importance of empathy in catering to the diverse needs of students, suggesting educators to develop culturally responsive teaching practices. Added on, the finding validates the study of Kozina et al. (2022) which underscored the significance of empathy in education, urging educators to be sensitive and empathic with their students' needs which have a favorable influence on their conduct, academic performance, and emotional health. Moreover, it fosters relationships between educators and students, student wellbeing, and a healthy learning environment.

Moreover, Noddings (2012) emphasized the consequences exhibiting empathy where educators established meaningful connections with their students, resulting in a more positive and supportive learning environment. Also, Huang (2011) indicated that educators who demonstrated empathy contributed to a positive classroom climate, leading to increased student engagement. While, Soh and Lim (2019) found that higher levels of empathy resulted to higher levels of teacher effectiveness and student engagement. Further, the study also found that empathy was essential for creating inclusive and supportive learning environments.

Practicing Resilience. Practicing resilience is always manifested among educators in private higher education institutions in Region XI. A high level of resilience among teachers implies that they can bounce back from setbacks, challenges, and adversity in their personal and professional lives. These teachers maintain a positive outlook and keep working towards their goals, even when faced with obstacles or setbacks. They also adapt to change and seek out opportunities for growth and learning. Moreover, teachers with a very high level of resilience are better equipped to manage challenges and to maintain a positive and productive work environment. They can also serve as positive

role models for their students, demonstrating the importance of perseverance and determination in the face of adversity.

The finding cited above validates the statement of Austin and Sorrell (2018) that resilience is a vital trait for teachers, allowing them to effectively navigate the challenges and stressors of their profession. Further, the finding supports the study of Broido et al. (2019) which emphasizes the importance of resilience for teachers in higher education, noting that resilience can help educators cope with difficult situations and maintain their emotional well-being. Furthermore, the results of the study coincide with the statement of Soh and Lim (2019) which highlighted the importance of resilience in the academic workplace, noting that it is essential for teachers to cope with the challenges of their work and maintain a positive attitude.

Moreover, Poon (2019) emphasizes that teachers who can practice resilience can serve as role models for their students, helping to promote positive emotional and mental health outcomes for them. This is also aligned with the study of Day and Hong (2016) that emotionally resilient teachers are better equipped to handle setbacks and challenges, which contributes to a more supportive and nurturing learning environment for students. Further, Luthar et al. (2020) underlined that emotionally resilient educators in higher education institutions can navigate challenges and setbacks, enabling them to maintain their well-being and perform at their best.

Level of Teaching Efficacy of Educators

The teaching efficacy of teachers in private higher education institutions in Region XI is measured in terms of efficacy for instruction, efficacy for motivation, and efficacy for classroom management. It appears that the overall level of teaching efficacy is very high, which means that teaching efficacy is always demonstrated by the educators in private higher education institutions in Region XI. A very high level of teaching efficacy among teachers implies that they have a strong belief in their ability to effectively teach their students and positively impact their learning outcomes. This also infers that teachers have a sense of confidence and competence in their abilities to create engaging and effective instructional experiences, to adapt their teaching to meet the diverse needs of their students, and to foster positive relationships with their students and colleagues.

The result supports the study conducted by Tschannen-Moran and Woolfolk Hoy (2018) which highlighted the value of teaching efficacy in students' learning outcomes, suggesting educators to use effective instructional strategies, leading to increased student engagement and achievement. On one hand, the finding supports the study of Johnson and Smith (2021) which stressed the value of teacher efficacy in classroom instructional practices, suggesting the educators to employ effective instructional strategies, engage in reflective practices, and create a positive classroom climate, leading to improved student learning outcomes.

Moreover, Brown and Johnson (2023) pointed out the relevance of teaching efficacy in teacher job satisfaction and burnout, urging school heads to give importance on fostering teaching effectiveness to promote teacher well-being. Similarly, Wilson and Thompson (2020) investigated the importance of the role of teaching efficacy in teacher retention and attrition, urging school heads to intensify the level of teaching efficacy of educators, resulting to educators' higher level of commitment and retention in the teaching profession.

Likewise, the results substantiate the efficacy theory of Bandura (1997) which posits that teachers with high teaching efficacy are more likely to persist in the face of challenges and setbacks and seek out professional development opportunities to improve their practice. Also, Bates et al. (2011) indicated that teachers with a very high level of teaching efficacy possess a strong belief in their ability to influence student learning outcomes. Likewise, Fraser et al. (2018) underscored that decrease in teaching efficacy may affect teachers' willingness to implement changes in the class and the school environment and decrease their voluntary participation in various school activities. Moreover, Cantrell et al. (2018) indicate that teachers with a very high level of teaching efficacy are more likely to embrace instructional innovations and implement effective teaching practices.

Efficacy for Instruction. The results indicate very high level of efficacy for instruction indicating that it is always demonstrated among educators in private higher education institutions in Region XI. A very high level of efficacy for instruction suggests that these teachers have a strong belief in their ability to positively impact their students' learning outcomes through effective instructional strategies. They are also more likely to engage in behaviors that are conducive to student learning, such as providing clear explanations, using varied teaching strategies, and giving feedback that helps students understand how to improve. Further, the results indicate that the teachers are more likely to persist in the face of challenges and setbacks, and to seek out professional development opportunities to improve their instructional practice, to be motivated and engaged in their work, leading to higher job satisfaction and retention.

The finding of the study strengthens the study conducted by Tschannen-Moran and Woolfolk Hoy (2018) which revealed the importance of the educators' high levels of efficacy for instruction, encouraging educators to use effective instructional strategies, leading to increased student engagement and achievement. Further, it validates the findings of Soh and Lim (2019) which advocated for teachers' high level of teaching efficacy, urging educators to persevere in the face of challenges and setbacks and seek out professional development opportunities to improve their instructional practices. Furthermore, Yoon (2019) highlighted the importance of teachers' teaching efficacy in instructional practices and student achievement. The author urged the educators use instructional strategies that promote student engagement and learning.

Similarly, Brew et al. (2020) the need for educators to possess high levels of instructional efficacy traits for successful skill acquisition. Also, Yack and Shaw (2017) emphasized that students that have a teacher with high efficacy for instruction performed better on achievement tests than their peers who are taught by teachers with low efficacy for instruction.

Efficacy for Motivation. The result indicates a very high level of efficacy for motivation implying that these teachers have a strong belief in their ability to motivate and engage with their students. This also implies that teachers can create a positive learning environment that fosters student engagement and academic success. These teachers are confident in their ability to create lessons and activities that are challenging and interesting to their students, which in turn can lead to higher levels of student motivation and achievement. Additionally, the results imply that the respondents are better able to understand and respond to the diverse needs of their students, creating a more inclusive and supportive classroom environment.

The results of the study validate the Efficacy Theory of Bandura (1993) which emphasizes that self-efficacy plays a crucial role in individuals' motivation and behavior. Similarly, Tschannen-Moran and Woolfolk Hoy (2018) have conducted research on teacher efficacy and found that it is positively related to student achievement and teacher effectiveness. Additionally, Henson and Eller (2019) have found that teachers with higher levels of efficacy are more likely to use effective instructional strategies, leading to increased student engagement and achievement. Furthermore, self-efficacy beliefs influence motivation and performance in various domains, including education. Teachers with a very high level of efficacy for motivation possess a strong belief in their ability to inspire and engage their students, which contributes to improved learning outcomes (Pajares, 2012).

Efficacy for Classroom Management. The result indicates a very high level of efficacy for classroom management among educators in private higher education institutions in Region XI. A very high level of efficacy for classroom management among teachers in higher education institutions implies that they are confident in their ability to create a positive and effective learning environment. This also implies that teachers who feel confident in their ability to manage their classrooms are more likely to establish clear expectations, set appropriate boundaries, and use effective disciplinary strategies when necessary.

Additionally, the results imply that with effective classroom management, the teachers potentially contribute to increased student engagement and improved relationships between teachers and students. Therefore, a high level of efficacy for classroom management among teachers in higher education institutions is an important factor in promoting student success.

The findings of the study substantiate on the statement of Evertson and Weinstein (2018) which emphasized that effective classroom management is critical for promoting student learning and achievement, urging educators to enhance their teaching efficacy which plays a major role in effective classroom management. Similarly, the finding confirms the study of Pekrun et al. (2019) that emphasized the importance of teacher self-efficacy thus, suggesting educators to create a positive learning environment and fostering student engagement. Finally, Everston and Weinstein (2006) as cited by Kratochwill et al. (2010), underscored the importance for teachers to build trusting, supportive relationships with their students as well as with other adults in the classroom. They should also plan and carry out lessons in a way that maximizes their students' access to learning.

Added on, Woolfolk Hoy and Davis (2018) claimed the importance of the teacher's teaching efficacy in classroom management which is essential for building positive teacher-student relationships and promoting academic achievement. Also, Emmer and Sabornie, (2015), stressed the idea of classroom management is strongly related to academic accomplishment, teacher effectiveness, and teacher and student behavior. Discipline has traditionally been viewed by educators as one of the most significant barriers to encouraging effective teaching. Proper Classroom management leads to class control and a conducive teaching-learning environment. Classroom management is a multi-faceted activity and extends beyond the traditional behavior management techniques recommended to deal with students with disruptive behavior

Significance of the Influence of Instructional Capacity and Emotional Quotient on Teaching Efficacy

The results of the regression analysis regarding the influence of instructional capacity and emotional quotient on teaching efficacy are discussed in this section. It appears that both instructional capacity and emotional quotient have an influence on teaching efficacy. The finding that both instructional capacity and emotional quotient significantly influence teaching efficacy implies that being a highly effective teacher requires a combination of both technical skills and emotional intelligence. Teachers who possess strong instructional skills, such as the ability to create effective lesson plans and use appropriate instructional strategies, are more likely to have high teaching efficacy. At the same time, teachers who possess a high level of emotional intelligence, including the ability to understand and manage their own emotions as well as empathize with their students, are also more likely to have high teaching efficacy.

The findings substantiate the study conducted by Yoon (2018) which found that teachers' emotional quotient was positively related to their self-efficacy. Similarly, the finding confirms the study of Soh and Lim (2019) and Poon (2018) have also highlighted the importance of both instructional capacity and emotional quotient in shaping teaching efficacy. The results of the study substantiate Vroom's Expectancies Theory (Vroom, 1964) which suggests that teachers with high levels of instructional capacity and emotional quotient are more likely to have positive expectancies about their ability to effectively teach their students.

The results conform with the study of Krishnan and Awang (2020) that both instructional capacity, including factors such as instructional strategies, classroom management, and assessment practices, and emotional quotient, encompassing emotional awareness, self-regulation, and interpersonal skills, significantly influenced teaching efficacy. Additionally, teachers with high levels of instructional capacity and emotional quotient are more likely to have the necessary resources and support to effectively teach their students, which can increase their belief in the instrumentality of their efforts.

Moreover, Vroom's Expectancy Theory suggests that both instructional capacity and emotional quotient can influence teaching efficacy by shaping teachers' beliefs about their ability to effectively teach their students, their perceived instrumentality of their efforts, and the valence of improved student learning outcomes.

The findings of the study are also consistent with Bandura's (1993) Theory of Self-efficacy which provides insights into how instructional capacity and emotional quotient influence teaching efficacy. According to Bandura, self-efficacy is the belief in one's ability to succeed in specific situations or accomplish particular tasks. In the context of teaching efficacy, teachers with high levels of self-efficacy believe that they can effectively manage their classrooms, use effective instructional practices, and positively impact their students' learning outcomes.

Lastly, the study of Brackett et al. (2011) conforms that of teachers' emotional quotient, in combination with their instructional capacity, significantly influences their teaching efficacy and its importance on integrating instructional capacity with emotional intelligence to enhance teaching effectiveness, foster self-efficacy beliefs, and ultimately impact student achievement

Lived Experiences of Educators Concerning Their Teaching Efficacy

The lived experiences of educators concerning their teaching efficacy is considered vital in this study. Six themes emerged from their descriptions of the participants concerning their teaching efficacy which are, embracing lifelong learning, showing empathy for learners, intensifying classroom management, alignment with organizational climate, curriculum-based learning, and maintaining emotional stability.

Embracing Lifelong Learning. As highlighted in the previous section, the participants' responses during the in-depth interview and focus group discussion highlight the participants' strong commitment among the participants to lifelong learning and continuous improvement in teaching efficacy. They recognize the need to explore new strategies, embrace mentorship, pursue professional development opportunities, and acknowledge that learning is an ongoing process. This attitude showcases their dedication to providing the best possible learning experiences for their students.

The findings of the study coincide with the statement of Sharan (2018) that educators need to desire for ongoing learning since education is not merely preparation for life but life itself. She further said that the dedication to continuous improvement, research-based practices, and adapting instruction to meet diverse learner needs are essential for effective teaching. The results further paralleled with the statement of Brookfield (2019) who emphasized that critically reflecting on assumptions and practices is important to improve teaching effectiveness.

In addition, Bain (2018) highlighted that reflection, experimentation, and adaptation based on student feedback for effective teaching occupy a space in instruction, hence, involvement in lifelong learning helps educators improve their teaching competence. Moreso, the finding of the study confirmed with the statement of Smith (2018) which emphasized the need for teachers to engage in continuous professional development to keep pace with the evolving educational landscape. Also, Spitzmuller et al. (2013) indicated the need for educators to engage in professional development to build proactive skills that emphasize prevention and respect as well as to organize their ideas regarding problematic behavior.

The findings of the study also parallel with the statement of Guskey (2018) that effective teaching in higher education requires a commitment to ongoing professional development. Further, Guskey emphasizes that effective professional development should be ongoing, job-embedded, and focused on improving teaching practices and student learning outcomes. Furthermore, the results validate the Efficacy Theory of Bandura (1997) which posits that teachers with high teaching efficacy are more likely to persist in the face of challenges and setbacks and seek out professional development opportunities to improve their practice. This can lead to a positive cycle of continuous improvement and growth for both teachers and students

Additionally, Joyce and Showers (2020) advocated for the use of research-based professional development models, such as the peer coaching or coaching partnership model. They argued that sustained professional development that includes coaching and collaborative reflection on teaching practices can lead to positive changes in educators' attitudes, resulting in improved teaching efficacy.

Furthermore, the results of the study coincide with the study of Robinson (2018) which highlighted the role of school leaders in advocating for and creating conditions that support effective professional development. She emphasized the importance of professional learning communities, where educators engage in collaborative professional development activities, share experiences, and learn from one another, which shaped their attitudes and beliefs about teaching efficacy. Moreover, Lieberman and Miller's (2018) work on teacher professional development emphasized the role of experiences and reflective practice in shaping educators' attitudes. They argued that professional development experiences, particularly those that involve collaborative reflection on teaching practices, can lead to changes in attitudes about teaching efficacy.

Showing Empathy for Learners. Based on the participants' responses, a second prominent theme emerges, which revolves around demonstrating empathy towards learners. The participants highly value and acknowledge the significance of students posing challenging questions, as it fosters a culture of curiosity and critical thinking within the classroom. Additionally, participants mentioned employing approaches such as translating concepts from English to Tagalog or even Bisaya to aid comprehension for students facing language barriers, thereby exemplifying their dedication to facilitating understanding.

Moreover, participants demonstrated a strong consideration for the emotional well-being of their students, recognizing and responding to their sensitivities and individual needs. To accommodate diverse learning styles and multiple intelligences, the participants also highlighted the use of differentiated instruction as an effective strategy. The data implies a student-centered approach to teaching, where participants prioritize student engagement, responsiveness, understanding, and differentiation to create a supportive and inclusive learning environment which indicates that the educators demonstrate empathy for their learners.

The results jibe with the statement of Banks (2018) which stressed the value of cultural diversity in the classroom, urging teachers to integrate diverse cultural perspectives into their curriculum and teaching practices. Further, Delpit (2018) emphasized the importance of bridging the gap between home culture and school culture to create an inclusive learning environment that values students' cultural backgrounds and experiences. Furthermore, Hattie (2019) advocated for visible learning, where teachers create explicit learning environments, set high expectations, provide feedback, and engage students actively in their learning.

Likewise, the finding confirms the study of Stanley et al. (2016) which stressed that the premise of teaching emotional quotient is compassion and empathy, and it is crucial for teachers to interact with pupils to understand their backgrounds and cultures. Similarly, Austin and Sorrell (2018) also revealed that empathy is a key factor in developing positive relationships between teachers and students. Similarly, a study by Soh and Lim (2019) found that higher levels of empathy were associated with higher levels of teacher effectiveness and student engagement. These findings suggest that a very high level of empathy among teachers in higher education institutions can have significant benefits for both teachers and students.

Furthermore, studies have also found that empathy is essential for creating inclusive and supportive learning environments. For instance, a study of Broido et al. (2019) found that empathy was critical in supporting LGBT students and promoting all-encompassing

practices in higher education institutions. In another study, Poon (2020) found that empathy was crucial in developing culturally responsive teaching practices that catered to the diverse needs of students. Overall, these studies highlight the importance of empathy in creating positive learning environments and promoting effective teaching practices in higher education settings.

Intensifying classroom management. The findings reveal that the participants' statements emphasize various strategies that contribute to enhancing teaching effectiveness, specifically focusing on intensifying classroom management. They highlight the significance of strengthening collaborative activities within the classroom to promote active learning and engagement. Additionally, the participants recognize and harness students' leadership skills, empowering them and fostering a sense of responsibility. Notably, the participants' willingness to draw inspiration from their colleagues' classroom management techniques reflects their reflective and growth-oriented approach to teaching. They also emphasize the value of constant classroom monitoring, demonstrating a commitment to ongoing assessment and adaptation.

By implementing these strategies, teachers can create dynamic and student-centered learning environments that encourage collaboration, leadership development, peer learning, open communication, and continuous monitoring. These findings suggest that educators should intensify their efforts in classroom management to effectively address the educational needs of their students.

Several authors have highlighted findings that align with the points mentioned. Danielson (2018) emphasized the significance of learning from colleagues and reflection for continuous improvement in classroom management. Further, Wong (2019) accentuated the significance of classroom management where establishing clear expectations, and monitoring student behavior were crucial to maintain a well-managed learning environment. Furthermore, Bain (2018) stressed the importance of creating an inclusive classroom environment that promotes student voice and active participation. Similarly, it conforms in the study of Wong and Wong's (2018) which emphasized the importance of setting clear expectations, building positive relationships with students, and implementing consistent routines to intensify classroom management and optimize student learning.

The goal of classroom management according to Brophy, 1996 as cited by Bozkus, K, (2020).is to help students develop self-control by encouraging good performance and behavior. Thus, the idea of classroom management is strongly related to academic accomplishment, teacher effectiveness, and teacher and student behavior. Proper classroom management according to Emmer & Sabornie, (2015) leads to class control and a conducive teaching-learning environment. Classroom management is a multi-faceted activity and extends beyond the traditional behavior management techniques recommended to deal with students with disruptive behavior It is important for teachers to build trusting, supportive relationships with their students as well as with other adults in the classroom. They should also plan and carry out lessons in a way that maximizes their students' access to learning.

Alignment with Organizational Climate. The statements of the participants are regard to their teaching efficacy led to the development of an important theme which is alignment with organizational climate. During the in-depth discussion, participants emphasized the importance of cultivating relationships based on respect and trust within

the institution. They expressed a willingness to go beyond their regular duties, demonstrating their commitment to serving in their roles. However, some participants also mentioned feeling pressure when interacting with other instructors. In the focus group discussion, participants highlighted the significance of creating an atmosphere free from barriers, where individuals feel comfortable expressing their opinions without fear of judgment or negative consequences. They emphasized the importance of establishing a student-friendly environment that prioritizes the needs and well-being of the students.

The results of the study strengthen the statement of Schein (2018) that the importance of trust, respect, and psychological safety in creating a positive organizational climate cannot be overstated. Further, Edmondson (2018) emphasized the significance of fostering a climate of psychological safety where employees feel secure to express their ideas and take interpersonal risks. He also highlighted the value of a culture of generosity and collaboration, where employees are motivated to go beyond their duties and support one another. Furthermore, Luthans (2020) stressed the creation of a positive work climate that nurtures employee engagement, resilience, and commitment.

These authors' works collectively support the significance of trust, respect, psychological safety, going beyond duties, and creating a positive organizational climate. Ali (2018) highlighted the importance of a conducive work environment, collaborative relationships, and opportunities for professional growth provided by the organization. This aligned that teaching efficacy and the organizational climate indicates the crucial role of the organizational context in shaping educators' performance and job satisfaction (Warrick, 2017).

Every individual within the school organization interacts with each other, making human relationships with each other so as to create a pleasant working environment and to make each individual or organization member feel comfortable and joyful in working to improve organizational performance (Puteh et al, 2014). However, if there are individuals who display behavior that is not fair in the atmosphere of interaction or human relations, it can be ascertained that the harmony of work, comfortable and at ease in doing organizational attitudes become obstructed. This is evident in one of the responses of the participants which is *feeling pressured when interacting with other instructors*.

O'Brennan et al. (2014) stressed that climate can be viewed on the one hand as an eternal characteristic that exemplifies a specific class, distinguishing it from other classes affecting the manner of teachers and students. On the other hand, the classroom climate is a feeling owned by teachers and students to the atmosphere of learning in that class. Shim et al. (2013) underscored that the comfortable and fun learning climate in the classroom is important because a healthy climate allows teachers to work fully and students can generate motivation for achievement in learning and teaching activities.

The creation of a harmonious and pleasant working atmosphere, according to Reinke et al. (2013) will improve the school's organizational performance, but it also happens that there is an atmosphere of work that impedes the improvement of school organizational performance, for example, because of a lack of support in the completion of a task or someone in the school which is not good, will disrupt the human relationships within the school organization and ultimately weaken the spirit and performance of the school organization, thus impacting on student learning outcomes.

For that a principal in carrying out his leadership duties, should pay attention and form a nice working environment in the school he leads (Garrett, 2008). This is very necessary considering the magnitude of school climate influences on the behavior of teachers, students, staff and all the elements associated with teaching and learning activities in schools. The pleasant work climate as projected comes from numerous leading factors in the school organization, which are, the principal's managerial skills and leadership (Razavipour & Yousef, 2017). Positive behaviors displayed by teachers, learners and staff at the school are a better welfare guarantee and are reinforced by complete and effective and efficient learning facilities and infrastructure.

Based on the prevailing account, it can be argued that the school's organizational climate befalls as a result of the observations and judgments of each member of the school organization, whether teachers, students, and employees, to the atmosphere around and within the organization of the school where work and study are done.

Curriculum Based-Learning. The participants' discussions on teaching efficacy had uncovered a significant theme in the study, namely curriculum-based learning. The statements made by the participants collectively demonstrate their dedication to various aspects of curriculum alignment, regulatory compliance, continuous improvement, student-centeredness, adaptability, and the effective integration of technology in education. These perspectives and practices shed light on the participants' approach to curriculum development and implementation.

The results of the study support several studies which emphasized the significance of teaching efficacy in curriculum-based learning. For example, Burgoyne and Stuart (2018) emphasize the importance of aligning higher education learning and teaching practices with the professional requirements of graduates. Further, they highlight the power of formative assessments in enhancing teaching efficacy by regularly assessing student progress and using feedback to adjust instructional approaches. Further, Bransford, Brown, and Cocking (2018) highlighted the need for alignment between instructional approaches and learners' cognitive processes, emphasizing the use of appropriate instructional materials and strategies.

Furthermore, Bates (2019) focuses on designing effective teaching and learning experiences in the digital age, promoting the integration of technology to enhance instructional delivery and student engagement. Together, these studies underscore the importance of curriculum alignment, formative assessment, inclusive teaching practices, and the effective use of technology in fostering teaching efficacy in curriculum-based learning. Lastly, Brown et al., (2022) examines the effective integration of technology in curriculum design and implementation. It discusses best practices, challenges, and strategies for utilizing technology to enhance teaching and learning experiences.

In fact, according to Mendez-Lopez et al. (2022). curriculum change would not result in meaningful educational innovation without a shift in the mindset of educators who act as curriculum designers, implementers, and evaluators.

Maintaining Emotional Stability. The theme that emerged from the discussions among participants regarding the teaching efficacy of educators is centered around maintaining emotional stability. The participants expressed their experiences and ideas related to this theme, highlighting several key aspects. Firstly, the educators expressed confidence in the support provided by their school, indicating a positive working environment where they feel assured that the institution will support them in their teaching

endeavors. This fosters a sense of trust and empowerment among educators, enabling them to effectively carry out their responsibilities.

Additionally, the participants expressed their enjoyment of fringe benefits provided in their workplace. This suggests that educators receive additional perks or rewards as part of their employment, contributing to their overall job satisfaction and well-being. Lastly, the educators emphasized their readiness to engage students in various activities. This reflects their proactive approach to creating dynamic and interactive learning experiences, demonstrating a strong commitment to student-centered instruction.

The results of the study validate the statement of Hattie (2019) that the educators' expression of confidence in the support received from the school suggests an assurance that the institution will back them up in their teaching endeavors, contributing to their overall job satisfaction and creating a conducive environment for effective teaching and learning.

Further, Fullan (2019) stated that the educators' readiness to engage students in different activities reflects their proactive approach to creating dynamic and interactive learning experiences, highlighting their commitment to student-centered instruction, and fostering an engaging and inclusive learning environment. Furthermore, Reeves (2018) averred that cooperation and happiness among educators signifies a positive team dynamic within the school, fostering collaboration, shared learning, and a supportive community of educators. This contributes to their overall job satisfaction and professional growth.

However, Costa and McCrae (2012) pointed out that the contrast of emotional stability is emotional instability, which is a common predictor of teacher exhaustion. Individuals low in emotional stability tend to express more negative emotions and may generally apply nonfunctional coping strategies. Ineffective coping strategies like denial or distancing themselves from the problem make them even more vulnerable to burnout. Schaufeli and Enzmann (2021) emphasized that teachers with low levels of emotional stability are prone to psychological stress and easily experience unpleasant emotions such as anger, anxiety, depression, and vulnerability. Emotionally unstable individuals tend to interpret neutral or even positive social encounters as threatening and have difficulties handling even minor frustrations.

Role of Experiences in Shaping the Beliefs of the Participants in Teaching Efficacy

The role of experiences in shaping the beliefs of participants in teaching efficacy was a significant focus of the discussions. Throughout these discussions, several themes emerged that highlighted the impact of experiences on shaping participants' beliefs. These themes include *embracing new perspectives, creating new mindsets, and awareness of school practices*. The participants recognized the transformative power of their experiences, leading to a shift in their perspectives, beliefs, and approaches to teaching. By acknowledging and understanding these themes, educators can further enhance their teaching efficacy and contribute to their professional growth.

Embracing a New Perspective. The participants' responses reflect their strong belief to adopting a fresh perspective on teaching efficacy. This belief

entails fostering a positive attitude, actively seeking personal and professional development opportunities, nurturing self-awareness, collaborating with school

management, and engaging in self-assessment. Collectively, these elements contribute to their unwavering dedication to continuous improvement, reflective teaching practices, and the creation of a positive and conducive learning environment. The data derived from the participants reflects the educators' efforts to improve their attitudes, engage in personal and professional development, foster self-awareness, collaborate with school management, and engage in self-assessment. These elements collectively shape their beliefs in teaching efficacy and underscore their dedication to continuous improvement and reflective teaching.

The participants' belief in actively seeking for professional development confirmed with the statement of Guskey (2018) that effective teaching in higher education requires a belief in ongoing professional development. Further, Guskey emphasizes that effective professional development should be ongoing, job-embedded, and focused on improving teaching practices and student learning outcomes.

Furthermore, several prominent authors in the field of education have examined factors that shape teachers' beliefs in teaching efficacy. For example, Hattie (2018) averred that attitude improvement and professional development are important in shaping the beliefs of teachers in teaching efficacy. Moreover, Marzano (2019) supported the idea of self-assessment and reflective teaching practices as important elements that shape the beliefs of teachers in teaching efficacy. Likewise, Hargreaves (2019) stressed the importance of collaboration and continuous improvement in teachers' teaching efficacy.

Meanwhile, the unwavering dedication of the participants to the creation of a positive and conducive learning environment supports the statement of Wong (2019) which emphasizes the significance of classroom management where establishing clear expectations and monitoring student behavior to maintain a well-managed learning environment.

Creating a New Mindset. The qualitative data collected from the participants' responses provide insight into their beliefs regarding teaching efficacy. The educators express the conviction that the strategies and practices employed by teachers directly impact their effectiveness in the classroom. They recognize that teaching efficacy ultimately relies on the capabilities and efforts of individual educators. Additionally, the participants emphasize the vital role played by school management in supporting their performance, believing that full support from the school administration leaves no room for poor performance. They also acknowledge the importance of aligning the school management's vision, mission, and goals with their own teaching practice. This alignment enables them to overcome challenges and maintain their commitment to effective teaching.

The findings coincide with some of the articles emphasizing the role of creating a new mindset in shaping the beliefs of educators on teaching efficacy. For example, Dweck and Blackwell (2018) emphasized that educators who cultivate a growth mindset, believing that their abilities and intelligence can be developed through effort and practice, are more likely to exhibit effective teaching practices. This mindset enables them to embrace challenges, persist in the face of setbacks, and seek out opportunities for growth and improvement.

Further, Liang and Hattie (2019) highlight the strong connection between teacher efficacy and mindset. They found that educators who possess a growth mindset, both about their own abilities and the potential for students' intelligence to be developed, are

more likely to engage in effective teaching practices and positively impact student outcomes. Moreover, Bates (2019) averred that creating a supportive work environment and providing opportunities for professional growth further shape the teachers' beliefs in teaching efficacy which in turn contributes to teachers' commitment to effective teaching practices.

Awareness of School Practices. Another theme that emerged from the participants' discussions on the role of experiences in shaping their beliefs in teaching efficacy is their awareness of school practices. The participants recognized the importance of being familiar with and knowledgeable about the specific practices and policies implemented within their school. They emphasized the significance of understanding the organizational structure, curriculum frameworks, and instructional approaches employed by the institution. This awareness enabled them to align their teaching strategies with the overall school goals and effectively navigate the educational landscape

The findings of the study are consistent with the statement of Bandura (1997) which highlights the significance of self-efficacy beliefs. In the context of teaching, educators who have positive experiences, such as successfully implementing effective teaching strategies or witnessing students' progress, are more likely to develop a strong sense of self-efficacy. This belief in their abilities to impact student learning and perform effectively as educators shapes their teaching efficacy. Similarly, Dweck (2018) emphasized the role of educators' experiences in relation to mindset. According to her research on mindset theory, educators who have experienced the benefits of a growth mindset, where they believe that abilities can be developed through effort and practice, are more likely to exhibit higher teaching efficacy.

Additionally, Hattie (2019) emphasizes the importance of educators' experiences and their impact on teaching efficacy. He highlights the role of teacher efficacy and its connection to effective teaching practices. Educators who have positive experiences, such as successfully implementing evidence-based teaching strategies or seeing a positive impact on student learning, develop a stronger belief in their own efficacy, which in turn enhances their teaching efficacy. This conforms the study of Pan et al., (2017) which emphasizes the significance of awareness of school practices among stakeholders for effective collaboration, decision-making, and school improvement efforts.

Role of Experiences in Shaping the Attitudes of the Participants in Teaching Efficacy

The findings from the focus group discussions and in-depth interviews uncovered three distinct themes regarding the role of experiences in shaping the attitudes of participants toward teaching efficacy. These themes are as follows: advocating professional development; establishing proactive relationships towards colleagues and students; and becoming more considerate of the needs of diverse learners. These themes emphasize the participants' acknowledgment of the significance of continuous growth, proactive engagement, and inclusivity in their teaching practices.

Advocating Professional Development. The participants' statements underscore the significance of advocating for professional development as a crucial factor in teaching efficacy. In the focus group discussion (FGD), one participant highlighted the

importance of continuous personal and professional growth. This implies that educators recognize the need to continually improve their teaching practices. By actively engaging in opportunities for personal and professional development, such as attending workshops or pursuing further education, educators can enhance their knowledge and skills, leading to increased effectiveness in teaching.

Additionally, another participant expressed a willingness to share responsibilities within the classroom. This suggests that educators understand the collaborative nature of teaching and the benefits of working together with colleagues, students, and other stakeholders. By sharing responsibilities and engaging in collaborative practices, such as lesson planning or problem-solving, educators can tap into collective expertise and resources, ultimately enhancing their teaching efficacy.

The results of the study strengthen Darling-Hammond (2017) who emphasized the significance of high-quality professional development in enhancing teaching effectiveness and student outcomes. Further, Joyce and Showers (2020) advocated for the use of research-based professional development models, such as the peer coaching or coaching partnership model. Furthermore, the results of the study coincide with Robinson's (2018) research on educational leadership which highlighted the role of school leaders in advocating for and creating conditions that support effective professional development.

Moreover, Lieberman and Miller's (2018) work on teacher professional development emphasized the role of experiences and reflective practice in shaping educators' attitudes. The above-mentioned authors claimed that professional development experiences, particularly those that involve collaborative reflection on teaching practices, can lead to changes in attitudes about teaching efficacy. Spitzmuller et al. (2013) pointed out that professional development is essential for staff to build proactive skills that emphasize prevention and respect as well as to organize their ideas regarding problematic behaviors.

Establishing Proactive Relationships with Colleagues and Students. The participants highlighted the crucial role of establishing proactive relationships with colleagues and students as a significant theme in shaping their attitudes toward teaching efficacy. The qualitative data gathered from the participants underscores the significance of building positive relationships and fostering understanding among educators. The participants emphasized the importance of establishing strong connections with colleagues, students, and other stakeholders in the educational setting. These relationships create a supportive and collaborative environment that enhances teaching efficacy.

The findings of the study jibe with Comer's (2018) work which emphasized the importance of establishing positive relationships with colleagues, students, and families in the educational setting. According to Comer, fostering proactive relationships with colleagues and students creates a sense of belonging, trust, and collaboration, which positively impacts educators' attitudes and teaching efficacy.

Further, the results support Marzano's (2019) research on effective teaching and learning which emphasizes the role of positive teacher-student relationships. The findings also support Aguilar's (2018) work which focuses on the importance of relational trust and building connections in education. Similarly, Barth's (2019) research on school culture and professional learning communities underscores the significance of establishing

proactive relationships among educators. Smith et al. (2016) indicated that schools must prioritize creating collaborative environments that foster trust, shared decision-making, and a sense of collective responsibility to enhance educators' attitudes and overall effectiveness in their teaching practices

Becoming More Considerate of the Needs of the Diverse Learners. The participants' descriptions of their experiences contribute to the development of a significant theme: becoming more considerate of the needs of diverse learners. This theme plays a crucial role in shaping the attitudes of educators toward teaching efficacy. By recognizing and understanding the unique needs and characteristics of diverse learners, educators can adapt their instructional strategies and approaches to cater to individual differences. This increased consideration for the needs of diverse learners leads to more inclusive and effective teaching practices, promoting student engagement, growth, and success. Participants emphasized the importance of going above and beyond their regular responsibilities, demonstrating a strong commitment to meet the needs of their students.

The results of the study support the statement of Ladson-Billings (2018) emphasizing the importance of culturally relevant pedagogy, which recognizes and addresses the diverse needs of learners. By becoming more considerate of the needs of diverse learners, educators can create inclusive and empowering learning environments that positively impact their attitudes which influences their teaching efficacy. The findings further support Gay's (2020) work which focused on culturally responsive teaching, which centers on acknowledging and embracing the cultural backgrounds and experiences of students. The findings also support Nieto's (2019) work which focused on the importance of multicultural education and social justice in teaching. The educators who become more considerate of the needs of diverse learners develop a sense of responsibility for promoting social justice and equitable educational opportunities, which positively shapes their attitudes toward teaching efficacy.

Role of Experiences in Shaping the Commitments of the Participants in Teaching Efficacy

The analysis of participants' discussions reveals the role of experiences in shaping their commitments to teaching efficacy. Three distinct themes emerged from these discussions, namely, the intensification of the code of ethics, demonstrating teaching effectiveness, and promoting lifelong learning. These themes signify the profound impact of participants' experiences on their dedication and determination to uphold professional values, exhibit effective teaching practices, and continuously engage in personal and professional growth. The participant's commitment to these themes highlights their understanding of the importance of ethical conduct, the demonstration of effective teaching methods, and the recognition of the ongoing pursuit of knowledge and development as integral aspects of being effective educators.

Intensification of Code of Ethics. The participants' experiences play a significant role in shaping their commitment to teaching efficacy, as reflected in the theme of intensification of the code of ethics. These experiences highlight the participants' deepening understanding and adherence to professional ethical standards in their teaching practice. By recognizing the importance of upholding ethical principles, such as

fairness, integrity, and respect, educators demonstrate a strong commitment to creating a positive and ethical learning environment. This theme underscores the participants' dedication to maintaining high moral standards and acting in the best interests of their students, contributing to their overall teaching efficacy.

Upholding the highest standards of quality education ensures excellence in teaching practices, curriculum development, and assessment methods. By focusing on these factors, professionals can cultivate a successful career while continually advancing their skills and providing quality education to students. This conforms in the study of Campbell, (2017) that the importance of deepening understanding and adherence to professional ethical standards in teaching practice, emphasizes the role of ethical reflection and decision-making in shaping educators' behavior and fostering professional growth.

The results also support the statement of Klassen et al. (2019) that educators who engage in continuing professional education demonstrate a strong commitment to teaching efficacy. As highlighted by Gay (2020), by staying updated with research, instructional strategies, and educational trends, they enhance their teaching skills and adapt to students' changing needs. Additionally, the results coincide with what Ashton and Webb (2019) stated that educators who uphold the highest standards of quality education are deeply committed to teaching efficacy.

Demonstrating Teaching Effectiveness. Another significant theme that emerged from the participants' statements is the demonstration of teaching effectiveness, which serves as a crucial experience shaping their commitment to teaching efficacy. The participants emphasized the importance of effectively delivering instruction, engaging students, and facilitating meaningful learning experiences. This theme highlights the participants' dedication to honing their teaching skills and continuously improving their instructional practices to ensure optimal student outcomes. Their commitment to demonstrating teaching effectiveness underscores their determination to provide high-quality education and contribute to students' overall academic growth and success.

The results of the study support Hoy and Woolfolk Hoy's (2019) assertion that teachers' experiences play a significant role in shaping their commitments to teaching efficacy. Further, the finding supports the statement of Tschannen-Moran Hoy (2018) that committed teachers also emphasize increasing student engagement by creating dynamic and interactive learning environments. Furthermore, the finding confirms the study of Rimm-Kaufman et al. (2015) which emphasized the importance of teacher-student interaction quality, including teachers' prioritization of student well-being, in promoting positive academic outcomes.

Lastly, Roffey (2012) explained positive relationships in creating a supportive and positive learning environment. In addition, the findings of the study support the assertions made by Henson et al. (2019) regarding committed teachers' focus on creating a positive learning environment that emphasizes students' well-being and emotional growth. Similarly, Ross (2018) highlighted the commitment of educators to being prepared, which reflects their dedication to thorough lesson planning and organizational skills. This level of preparedness according to Ladson-Billings (2018) allows the teachers to deliver high-quality instruction and adapt to the diverse needs of their students.

Promoting Lifelong Learning. The participants' statements regarding their experiences reveal the emergence of a significant theme: "Promoting Lifelong Learning." This theme highlights the profound impact of educators' experiences on shaping their

commitment to teaching efficacy. It underscores the notion that teachers' ongoing learning experiences, both within and outside the classroom, play a pivotal role in their professional growth and effectiveness as educators. The theme emphasizes the continuous development and improvement of teachers as they actively engage in learning, reflecting, and refining their teaching practices throughout their careers. By embracing the ethos of lifelong learning, educators deepen their commitment to providing high-quality education and fostering positive learning outcomes for their students.

These finding jibes with the statement of Gibson and Dembo (2018) that experienced educators demonstrate their commitment to the profession by engaging in mentoring younger teachers and supporting colleagues in subject leadership. Collectively, these findings highlight how the accumulation of experience nurtures a commitment to teaching efficacy, enabling educators to continually evolve and positively impact their students' learning journeys. Moreover, these findings support the statement of Tschannen-Moran and Hoy (2018) which underscore that experienced teachers prioritize learning and foster inclusive environments, indicating their recognition of education's transformative potential and their commitment to promoting equity. Lastly, the role of experienced teachers in recognizing education's transformative potential and their commitment to promoting equity through their instructional practices (Darling-Hammond,, 2017).

Joint Display of Salient Quantitative and Qualitative Findings

The collected data presents noteworthy quantitative and qualitative findings. These aspects encompass instructional capacity, teachers' emotional quotient, and teaching efficacy.

Instructional Capacity. The salient finding across both quantitative and qualitative data in the aspect of instructional capacity includes the active involvement of educators in professional development activities, specifically related to instructional management practices. This involvement is also highlighted in the lived experiences of educators concerning their teaching efficacy, aligning with the theme of embracing lifelong learning. Furthermore, another significant finding under the instructional capacity aspect is the monitoring of teachers' instructional practices in the classroom, which received a very high rating. This finding is also emphasized in the role of experiences in shaping the beliefs of the participants in teaching efficacy, particularly regarding self-assessment and reflection on one's teaching efficacy within the context of embracing new perspectives.

The finding of the study supports the statement of Danielson (2018) that effective teaching requires continuous learning and evaluation of its impact on student learning. The result further validates the idea of Marzano (2019) stating that teachers who emphasized instructional strategies that have a strong research base are more likely to achieve gains in student achievement. Furthermore, Wiliam (2019) highlighted the importance of ongoing assessment and feedback. According to him, the fundamental purpose of any assessment must be to support learning, and he advocated for the use of formative assessment as a tool to improve student learning and enhance teacher effectiveness.

Teacher's Emotional Quotient. The salient finding across both quantitative and qualitative data under the aspect of teachers' emotional quotient is that teachers prioritize doing the most difficult work first, as indicated by a high rating. This finding is also highlighted in the lived experiences of teachers regarding their teaching efficacy, specifically in the context of being willing to serve beyond the call of duty, aligning with the theme of alignment with organizational climate. Furthermore, another significant finding under the teachers' emotional quotient aspect is that teachers are skilled at resolving differences with others, as evidenced by a high rating. This finding is supported by qualitative data that emphasize the core idea of using differentiated instruction to cater to the multiple intelligences of students, reflecting the theme of showing empathy for learners.

The desire of educators to make a difference in the lives of learners by fostering an emotional connection aligns with the ideas of several prominent authors. Notably, the result confirms the study of Noddings (2017) which emphasized the ethics of care in education, advocating for caring relationships between teachers and students as a foundation for effective teaching and learning. Further Seligman, et al. (2019) highlights the significance of positive teacher-student relationships in promoting student well-being and academic success. The result of the study coincides with the statement of Dweck (2018) which underscored the importance of fostering a growth mindset in students and believes in their capacity to learn and grow. Further, the result corroborates with the study conducted by Blackwell et al. (2017) which revealed how a growth mindset predicts academic success throughout the adolescent transition by encouraging students to believe in their ability to learn and grow.

The salient finding across both quantitative and qualitative data under the aspect of teaching efficacy is related to the efficacy for motivation indicator. It indicates that teachers possess the ability to help their students value learning, with a very high rating. This finding is also evident in the role of experiences in shaping the attitudes of participants in teaching efficacy, specifically emphasizing the core idea of considering the readiness of students' minds and hearts and fostering students' appreciation for their own learning. This aligns with the theme of becoming more considerate of the needs of diverse learners.

Another significant finding under the teaching efficacy aspect is that teachers are capable of implementing alternative strategies in the classroom, as indicated by a very high rating. This finding is further supported by the lived experiences of educators regarding their teaching efficacy, highlighting the core idea of using appropriate instructional materials and teaching strategies that align with students' needs. This finding resonates with the theme of curriculum-based learning this indicate merging converging. Further, the results of the study support the statements of Delpit (2019) which emphasized the importance of understanding and addressing the diverse needs and experiences of students. Delpit asserted that effective teachers must be able to listen to and build on students' cultural and experiential knowledge. Furthermore, Tomlinson (2019) advocated for differentiated instruction, which involves adjusting teaching approaches to meet the diverse needs of learners.

Conclusions

The study highlights high level of instructional capacity of educators in higher education institutions in Region XI. They demonstrate strong instructional management practices, teacher quality, curriculum-material quality and quantity, instructional climate, student's learning readiness, and financial resources. Additionally, educators exhibit a remarkably high level of emotional quotient, possessing self-awareness, handling emotions, self-motivation, empathy, and resilience. Moreover, they show a high level of teaching efficacy in instruction, motivation, and classroom management. These findings point toward a solid foundation for effective teaching and learning, with educators well-equipped with emotional skills, fostering a conducive learning environment, and promoting student success.

The study highlights that both instructional capacity and emotional quotient significantly influence the teaching efficacy of educators in higher education institutions in Region XI. The findings indicate that educators with a high level of instructional capacity, encompassing instructional management practices, teacher quality, curriculum-material quality and quantity, instructional climate, student's learning readiness, and financial resources, are more likely to demonstrate a strong teaching efficacy. Similarly, educators with a high level of emotional quotient, including self-awareness, handling emotions, self-motivation, using empathy, and practicing resilience, also exhibit a greater teaching efficacy. These results underscore the importance of developing both instructional capacity and emotional quotient in educators to enhance their effectiveness in the classroom and ultimately contribute to improved student outcomes.

The analysis of the lived experiences of educators regarding their teaching efficacy reveals several essential themes. These themes include the significance of embracing lifelong learning, the value of demonstrating empathy towards learners, the need for intensifying classroom management, the importance of alignment with the organizational climate, the focus on curriculum-based learning, and the maintenance of emotional stability. These themes underscore the multifaceted nature of teaching efficacy and provide valuable insights into the factors that contribute to educators' effectiveness in the classroom. By recognizing and addressing these themes, educational institutions can foster a supportive environment that empowers educators to continuously grow, connect with students on a deeper level, effectively manage their classrooms, align with organizational goals, emphasize curriculum-based teaching strategies, and maintain emotional well-being.

The study emphasizes the significant role of experiences in shaping the beliefs, attitudes, and commitments of educators toward teaching efficacy. By embracing diverse and meaningful experiences, educational institutions foster a culture of continuous growth, reflection, and open-mindedness. This leads to enhanced teaching efficacy, professional development, and meeting the diverse needs of students.

The analysis of both quantitative and qualitative findings reveals several salient aspects related to instructional capacity, teachers' emotional quotient, and teaching efficacy. Regarding instructional capacity, the findings highlight the significance of school management conducting professional development studies of teachers, indicating a commitment to continuous improvement and enhancing instructional practices.

Additionally, the importance of school management monitoring teachers' instructional practices emphasizes the need for accountability and quality assurance in the educational setting. In terms of teachers' emotional quotient, the findings demonstrate a commonality among teachers in their recognition of the challenging nature of their work and their ability to effectively resolve differences with others.

These findings underscore the importance of emotional intelligence and interpersonal skills in fostering positive relationships and creating a supportive learning environment. Regarding teaching efficacy, the findings underscore the role of teachers in helping students value learning and the necessity of implementing alternative strategies in the classroom.

Recommendations

In the light of the foregoing findings and conclusions, the following recommendations were offered:

1. Since the findings revealed a high level of instructional capacity among educators in higher education institutions in Region XI, this may be enhanced to a very high level. School heads may prioritize continuous professional development for teachers through ongoing training programs, foster collaborative learning communities to encourage the sharing of insights and innovative practices, promote student-centered approaches that address diverse learning needs, allocate sufficient financial resources for instructional needs, including updated teaching materials and technology, and establish a robust evaluation and feedback system to guide educators in continuous improvement. By implementing these steps, school heads may effectively leverage educators' strong instructional capacity, leading to improved educational outcomes and enhanced student success.

2. Considering that both instructional capacity and emotional quotient significantly influence the teaching efficacy of educators in higher education institutions in Region XI, school heads play a crucial role in developing and enhancing these aspects. They may prioritize the implementation of targeted professional development or upskilling programs to improve instructional capacity and promote effective teaching strategies.

Additionally, school heads may facilitate workshops and training sessions that focus on enhancing the emotional quotient of educators, fostering self-awareness, emotional regulation, empathy, and resilience. Creating a supportive and collaborative school environment, allocating resources for instructional capacity development, and implementing a comprehensive evaluation system that assesses both aspects are also essential. By taking these steps, school heads may empower educators to enhance their teaching efficacy and positively impact student outcomes in higher education institutions in Region XI.

3. On the account that the analysis of educators' lived experiences highlights important themes that contribute to teaching efficacy, it is recommended that educational institutions may take steps to address these factors and improve the overall learning experience for students. Promoting empathy towards learners can be achieved through training programs that enhance educators' understanding of diverse student needs and perspectives. Intensifying classroom management can be supported by offering

resources, strategies, and mentorship to help educators create a positive and well-managed learning environment. Prioritizing curriculum-based learning can involve curriculum reviews, alignment with educational standards, and providing educators with access to relevant and updated teaching materials. Lastly, maintaining emotional stability can be supported by promoting a culture of well-being, offering counseling services, and creating opportunities for self-care and stress management for educators.

4. Since experiences play a pivotal role in shaping beliefs, attitudes, and commitment of educators in teaching efficacy, educational institutions may encourage educators to embrace new perspectives, develop a growth mindset, and increase awareness of effective school practices through diverse and meaningful experiences. Moreover, school heads may advocate for relevant professional development and promote student engagement considering their diverse learning needs.

5. Since the analysis of both quantitative and qualitative findings reveals salient aspects related to instructional capacity, teacher's emotional quotient, and teaching efficacy, it is recommended that teachers and school heads may collaborate to enhance educational practice. Teachers may actively engage in professional development programs to improve their instructional capacity and stay updated with the latest educational trends. School heads may establish mechanisms to monitor and evaluate teachers' instructional practices to ensure quality and promote continuous improvement. Both teachers and school heads may prioritize emotional quotient training to enhance interpersonal skills and create a positive classroom climate. Additionally, implementing student-centered approaches and encouraging adaptability and innovation in teaching strategies will foster active learning and student engagement.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This work was submitted to the UIC - REC in order to make sure that all areas of research ethics were properly followed. Additionally, while dealing with the subjects, the researcher took steps to ensure that the necessary ethical procedures were followed, citing study-related issues and safeguarding the anonymity of the research findings. Thus, the elements of ethical considerations were scrupulously upheld.

Social Value. The result of this study presented valuable information that guided school administrators on the use of appropriate instructional capacity to improve teachers' individual work performance, especially when they faced work conflict that affected the quality of their teaching efficacy. This also provided insights to teachers on how they could cope with emotions and how they could rely on their capacity as a teacher in order to maintain a higher level of work performance which in turn, would ensure a higher quality of student outcomes. The findings of the study were disseminated through forums and publications.

This study may offer insights among the teachers in higher education institutions as baseline information for decision-making and policy enhancement to strengthen teaching capacity. This study may provide consciousness among the participants on the effect of instructional capacity and emotional quotient on teaching efficacy. The results might potentially contribute to the body of knowledge already available about teaching

effectiveness. Further, there is an urgent need for research into the impact of instructional capacity and emotional quotient on teaching efficacy, particularly among higher education teachers in Region XI.

Informed Consent. The researcher obtained both written and verbal consent from the participants of this study. More specifically, a standard informed consent form was obtained from the UIC REC office, which was used in getting their voluntary permission to participate in the study. Consent was obtained before the conduct of the survey, FGD, and IDI. The ICF disclosed the purpose of the study, procedures, risks and benefits, privacy and confidentiality, and other valuable information to help the participants decide whether to participate in the study or not as participants.

Vulnerability of the Research Participants. To ensure the study's objectivity, justice, and fairness, the necessary consent from the relevant parties was obtained for this one. The researcher gave the assurance that neither the interview guide nor the questionnaires contained any offensive language. Additionally, the researcher took into account the vulnerability of the participants, and as a result, they were given the choice of whether to freely participate in the study, withdraw from it, or not participate at all. Additionally, because the participants in this study were over the age of 18, qualified teachers, and not exposed to emotional or psychological vulnerability, they were not vulnerable. The researcher further ensured that the participants' identities were kept secret and that they had protection from any chance of being identified.

Risks, Benefits, and Safety. Prior to conducting the study, the researcher secured the participants' consent and informed them of its aim or purpose. The participants were not forced to participate, and their safety was ensured because there was a possibility that they may have been intimidated or led to believe they had to take part in the study. They chose a time that worked best for them to do the IDI and FGD. A group of experts also examined the guide questions used in the IDI and FGD to ensure that they would cause the least amount of harm. The researcher used caution throughout the permissions procedure as well as the research technique itself, carefully weighing all of the advantages and risks involved. Participants were also informed of any possible hazards like discomfort, inconvenience, embarrassment, or anxiety. The researcher pledged to take all necessary precautions to reduce these potential risks in order to avoid these issues.

Furthermore, the results and recommendations were communicated to CHED - Region XI. Such a step was very advantageous for the creation of initiatives, programs, and projects that might increase the leadership effectiveness of the HEIs. In light of the study's findings, the participants were able to assess their efficacy as instructors. The school administration was aware of how instructional capacity affected teachers' abilities to instruct students effectively. Moreso, educators under their leadership were more effective because they had their complete support. Lastly, the participants' linked HEIs received a hard copy of the finished study. The researcher also took into account any potential future collaborative research related to the topic.

Privacy and Confidentiality of Information. The participant's privacy and confidentiality were protected in accordance with the provision in the Data Privacy Act of 2012. In order to ensure the protection of the research participants, coding was applied. Data was stored using protected electronic storage methods. The recorded video of the IDI and FGD, as well as the transcripts of their responses, were stored in a password-

protected folder. The researcher also assured that the names and details of the participants were dealt with utmost confidentiality. In particular, the researcher ensured the participants that their names and responses will be kept anonymous. Moreover, the questionnaires with substantial data, transcriptions, pictures, and recordings that were retrieved were securely kept by the researcher. Most importantly, the researcher assured the participants that the data gathered will solely be utilized for this research study only. Lastly, when the results of the research were published or discussed at conferences, no identifiable information were used

Justice. To avoid impartiality in choosing the participants, the researcher regarded all participants as equal whether they participate in the survey, IDI, or FGD. By using the right sample methods to choose participants for both the quantitative and qualitative parts of this study, the researcher upheld fairness. On one hand, the participants were selected according to the inclusion criteria which were mentioned in Chapter 2. The research was completed or conducted in the appropriate atmosphere with sufficient facilities and experience, and it was done with the utmost rigor and expertise. On the other hand, the participants were treated fairly by the researcher regardless of their position or level within the institution. The participants received equivalent tokens of appreciation or any other kind of acceptable and appropriate incentive because the researcher expended time and effort on them and even interrupted their routines. The costs associated with the data collection process that participants incurred were reimbursed through Gcash, or given to them personally.

Transparency. Any form of communication on the research was done in an honest and transparent manner in order to provide transparency in this study. The researcher showed to the participants the results after the data were gathered and correctly applied the methodologies that were employed in this study in order to protect the welfare of the participants. Included were all the records required to support data analysis. The results were also thoroughly reviewed, with special attention paid to data that may be accessible at the university library and that may have an impact on how the results were presented. In addition, the researcher outlined the scope of her engagement and how she upheld objectivity throughout data analysis and presentation of the study's findings. Transparency was ensured by reporting all information. The researcher saw to it that the inconvenience be addressed as soon as possible. Most importantly, there was no conflict of interest since the study was not funded. It was shouldered by the researcher.

Qualification of the Researcher. The researcher was motivated to conduct the study since this field was in relation to her profession as an educator in a private higher education institution in Davao City, specifically, the University of the Immaculate Conception. The researcher has been a full-time faculty of Jose Maria College Foundation, Inc. The researcher recognized her limited exposure to the mixed methods approach. Consequently, the researcher sought guidance and direction from her mentor and expert panelists, as well as peers who were proficient in this method. Hence, the researcher was very diligent and was open to any suggestions from her adviser and expert panelists to help improve the study. The researcher also had passed the comprehensive examination and was trained in this field of expertise. Most importantly, the researcher was qualified to do the task because of the help of her doubly qualified adviser who was a veteran when it comes to research studies. Her adviser was more than qualified to be a research adviser, as seen in her curriculum vitae. To conclude, she

decided to pursue this study because she was assured of the readiness of her adviser to assist her towards the completion of the study.

Adequacy of Facilities. The researcher assured that the materials required for this study were accessible and readily available. In the university where the researcher studied, there were books, online journals, and unpublished dissertations available for further readings and references that provided a variety of literatures and studies that supported the association of the variables utilized in the study. In addition to in-person interactions, online data collecting was also carried out. Computers, survey administration tools like Google Forms, and video-communication services like Zoom and Google Meet were available and essential in carrying out this study. There were also tools for data storage and security such audio recorders, cameras, computers, printers, and related software packages.

In order to assist the researcher in carrying out the study and disseminating results, a group of specialists who offered insightful recommendations and feedback were recruited.

Community Involvement. The researcher was committed to respecting the community, especially the school administrators and educators in higher education institutions in Region XI. All activities that were done were subject to the permission of the school's administration. With this, the school administrators will be informed of the results of the study for further improvement in the areas of institutions' instructional capacity and educators' performance, especially in their teaching efficacy. Community involvement was an important ingredient to the long-term success of an organization and should be an integral part of the community it served. Getting involved and establishing strong linkages with stakeholders through participation and involvement in community events allowed collaboration within the academic community.

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